

Safe-, sUstainable- and R recyclable-by design P olymeric systems
A guidance towardS next generation of plastics

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**Physical-Chemical properties of IAS and NIAS in
relation to their functionality and human and
environmental toxicity**

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Executive summary

This report presents the part of the hazard assessment performed in the frame of the SSRbD SURPASS approach. It complements reports D4.2 on identification of exposure scenarios and release assessment, D4.3 on hazard assessment using existing data and in vitro approaches and reports D4.5 and D4.6 on environmental assessment by LCA and economic assessment by LCC.

The EC Joint Research Centre (JRC) safe and sustainable by design (SSbD) framework consists of an iterative process of (re)design and safety and sustainability assessment phases along the innovation process. The (re-)design phase consists of the application of guiding principles to steer the development process. The goal, the scope and the system boundaries – which will frame the assessment of the chemical or material – are defined in this phase. The assessment phase comprises of: risk assessment (hazard, workers exposure during production, exposure during use) and environmental life-cycle assessment. The assessments can be carried out either on newly developed chemicals and/or materials, or on existing chemicals and/or materials to improve their safety and sustainability performance during production, use and/or end-of-life.

Following the risk assessment component of the JRC framework, hazard of ingredients was assessed using a stepwise approach. Starting with the collection of existing data, which was lacking for most substances, we performed modelling of the Quantitative Structure Activity Relation (QSAR) (described in D4.4) and in vitro and ecotoxicity testing (described in D4.3).

QSAR modelling was conducted for ingredients (intentionally added substances, IAS) and, if known, contaminants (non-intentionally added substances, NIAS). As QSAR modelling requires information on chemical structure, not for all substances hazard information could be obtained. This deliverable described the results of QSAR modelling for the three SURPASS case studies and the evaluation of the outcomes using a scoring system. In addition, the feasibility to relate hazard to physical chemical properties was explored and, specifically for CS3, an exposure assessment was conducted.

Case Study 1

CS1 addresses the building sector. In this CS, polyurethane-based window frames are intended to replace those made of PVC, wood or aluminium. All ingredients, except for polyol D (the only polyol assessed), resulted in the identification of a potential ecotoxicological hazard with QSAR modelling. The potential ecotoxicological hazard of the catalysts differed, where cystamine had the highest hazard score and THEED the lowest. A comparison between production routes could not be made due to a lack of data on all ingredients.

Case Study 2

CS2 focuses on the railway sector. The aim of this CS is to develop a composite material that is lighter than metal and can be used in structural applications, thus enabling a significant reduction in vehicle weight and energy consumption over its lifetime. All substances assessed with QSAR modelling resulted in a potential ecotoxicological hazard. However, adding the ecotoxicological hazards scores

for the reference route and alternative routes, showed that the total scores were lower (less hazardous) for the alternative routes.

Case Study 3

CS3 focuses on the packaging sector. CS3 is aimed at processing polyolefin multi-nanolayer (MNL) films for food packaging, barrier layer (EVOH or PA) with less compatibilizer. For some substances the potential ecotoxicological hazard level was higher than the water solubility, resulting in no potential hazard. All other substances detected in the migration samples, were found to have a potential ecotoxicological hazard. Although an ecotoxicological hazard could be considered less relevant for food packaging material, it should be noted that the tests described in D4.3 did not give any effect due to the relatively high toxicity of the solvent. Therefore, potential human hazards could have been missed.

List of acronyms

BW	Body Weight
DTU	Danish Food Institute
EC50	Effect Concentration inducing 50% effect
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
EU-CSS	EU - Chemical Strategy for Sustainability
GC-MS	Gas chromatography mass spectrometry
IAS	Intentionally added substances
JRC	EU Joint Research Centre
LC50	Lethal Concentration inducing 50% mortality
LOEC	Lowest observed effect concentration
mLLDPE	Metallocene Linear Low Density Polyethylene
MNL	MultiNanoLayered
NIAS	Non-intentionally added substances
NOEC	No Effect Concentration
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PA	Polyamide
PE	Polyethylene
PNEC	Predicted No Effect Concentration
PoD	Point of Departure
PU	Polyurethane resins
PVC	Polyvinyl chloride
QSAR	Quantitative Structure–Activity Relation
SMILES	Simplified Molecular Input Line Entry System
SSbD	safe-and-sustainable-by-design
SSIA	Safe(r) and Sustainable Innovation Approach
SSRbD	Safe-, Sustainable-, and Recyclable-by-Design
SVHC	Substance of Very High Concern
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
USEPA	United States Environmental Protection Agency

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1. Introduction

1.1 Background

The safe-and-sustainable-by-design (SSbD) concept integrates functionality with safety and sustainability aspects at an early phase of the innovation and product development process in order to minimize potential hazard(s) and/or exposure and to maximize sustainability. The Horizon Europe project SURPASS aims to develop a Safe-, Sustainable-, and Recyclable-by-Design (SSRbD) assessment and guidance dedicated to plastic materials. SURPASS focuses on 3 case studies: 1) Building sector: New recyclable-by-design bio-sourced polyurethane resins (PU) with enhanced vitrimer properties to replace polyvinyl chloride (PVC) for window frames, 2) Transport sector: New fire-resistant recyclable epoxy-vitrimer based composites integrating non-releasable fire-retardancy moieties, as alternative to metal for the train structure, and 3) Packaging sector: MultiNanoLayered (MNL) films optimizing their composition and compatibilizer content to make films efficient and recyclable, replacing current multi-layers films that today face uncertainty in recycling with respect to partially challenging designs and compositions, or lack of sorting and dedicated processing. In line with the framework from the EU Joint Research Centre (JRC), we have developed an SSRbD strategy that considers exposure and release, hazard and life-cycle assessment and costing, taking into account the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the development stage of each case study (Soeterman-Hernandez, 2025). The focus of the current work is to develop a hazard assessment strategy in an SSRbD context allowing integration of hazard evaluation during the development process.

The SSbD concept is described in the EU - Chemical Strategy for Sustainability (EU-CSS). JRC has developed a framework for SSbD criteria where an integrated and iterative two-phase approach is recommended consisting of: i) a (re)-design phase in which guiding principles are proposed and ii) a step-wise hierarchical approach to address chemical safety, direct toxicological/ecotoxicological impact, and aspects of environmental sustainability (Caldeira, 2022) (Figure 1.1-1). A need for a mindset change, to ensure that newly developed materials combine functionality with safety and sustainability from the innovation phase, is also taken into account by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) through the Safe(r) and Sustainable Innovation Approach (SSIA) (OECD, 2022). These approaches from JRC and OECD form the basis for the integrated approach developed in SURPASS, together with the CEN 1325 (CEN 2014) and ISO 15686-5 standards.

Figure 1.1-1: Iterative approach of SSbD, as proposed by JRC (European Commission: Joint Research Centre, Abbate, E., Garmendia Aguirre, I., Bracalente, G., Mancini, L. et al., *Safe and sustainable by design chemicals and materials – Methodological guidance*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2024, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/28450>).

The focus of hazard assessment in SURPASS is mainly on step 1 of the framework proposed by JRC. Together with D4.2 and D4.3, this work falls under steps 1, 2 and 3 of the framework (Figure 1.1-1). Hazard evaluation in the SSRbD context is applied to three selected case studies.

1.2 Sources of hazard data

For hazard evaluation, different sources of hazard data were used, the main ones being the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) database, Quantitative Structure–Activity Relation (QSAR) modelling and *in vitro* testing. Ideally, these steps follow a tiered approach, parallel to the increasing TRL of the product development process. Existing hazard information was collected in an early stage of the project to allow feedback on potential hazards to the case study teams. Subsequent steps, namely QSAR modelling and *in vitro* testing, were conducted in parallel. A schematic overview of the approach is shown in Figure 1.2-1

Figure 1.2-1: Hazard assessment approach followed in the SURPASS project. The focus is on the green part, whereas in collaboration with D4.2 and D4.3 the orange parts are addressed for specific questions and case studies. D4.4 addresses steps 5, 5a and 7 of the diagram. A more detailed explanation of the diagram can be found in D4.3.

2. QSAR modelling

2.1 QSAR model choices

Testing for environmental hazards

In chemical risk assessment the ecotoxicological hazard is first approached by looking at three different aquatic species, representing three different trophic levels. Mostly algae, crustaceans and fish are used to represent these three different trophic levels. Toxicity testing then covers acute toxicity (72 hours algae growth test, 48 hours daphnia immobility test, and 96 hours fish mortality test). These tests should yield a 50% effect dose (growth, mobility, mortality respectively) that are used for the first tier ecotoxicological risk assessment. When more data is generated, standardized chronic toxicity testing follows, with longer duration: 96 hrs for algae, ~14 days for crustaceans (depending on species), and ~14-21 days for fish (depending on species). From these tests a No Observed Effect Concentration (NOEC) is derived, which can be based on all possible (adverse) effects, but effectively mortality or reproduction (for both fish and crustaceans) and growth rate (for algae) are the effect parameters that dominate the NOECs derived. The lowest no-effect concentration of the three test results is subsequently used to determine the Predicted No Effect Concentration (PNEC) which is the Point of Departure (PoD) for the aquatic environment risk assessment. When no chronic experimental data is required, or available, a generic 10-fold acute-to-chronic ratio is used to estimate a chronic NOEC from

acute toxicity testing results. This procedure is in detail described e.g. in the EU REACH Guidance documents on [REACH Guidance on Information Requirements and Chemical Safety Assessment, Determination of *Predicted No-effect-Effect levels* (PNEC) in Chapter R.10 and the corresponding chapters of integrated testing strategies for the environment endpoints (Sections R.7.8 to R.7.11 in Chapter R.7b and R.7c), see Guidance on Information Requirements and Chemical Safety Assessment - ECHA.].

QSAR modelling for environmental hazards

The QSAR modelling in this deliverable focussed on environmental hazards. As the species/endpoints mentioned above are the most abundant experimental data available, QSAR models for ecotoxicity reflect this procedure and mostly either focus on predicting acute L/EC50 values for fish, daphnids and algae, either using average toxicity for the three species representing different trophic levels (fish, daphnids and algae) or predicting the acute toxicity for a specific daphnid, fish or algae species. The abundance of chronic aquatic toxicity data is much less than for acute toxicity data, therefore also less QSAR models (and less reliable QSAR models) are available for predicting chronic aquatic toxicity.

Nevertheless, a plethora of publicly available QSAR models for these endpoints is available, and we have selected a number of well known, well documented aquatic toxicity models to generate multiple QSAR estimates for each constituent in the SURPASS products.

Subsequently the QSAR results are treated as if they were experimental results, effectively using the lowest predicted NOEC as the basis for the PNEC / PoD to characterize the *potential* ecotoxicological hazard of each constituent. These PNECs can be directly compared to each other when prioritizing ecotoxicological hazard, or can be used as the basis for the SURPASS-scoring system (see section 3 in this deliverable).

The list of QSAR models (software) applied is:

- **ECOSAR v2.2**, from USEPA, yielding both acute and chronic estimates for fish, Daphnids and algae toxicity. Download and Operation Manual as well as the Methodology document are available from <https://www.epa.gov/tsca-screening-tools/ecological-structure-activity-relationships-ecosar-predictive-model>. The chronic models from ECOSAR actually predict a ChV (mg/L) value, which is the geometric mean between the NOEC and the Lowest observed effect concentration (LOEC). To translate this back to a true NOEC prediction one would have to know the dose-spacing, which is not given. But as it is common practice in chronic toxicity to use a factor of 3 between low, medium and high dose, the ChV value is divided by a factor of squareroot (3)=1.73 to derive an estimated NOEC. ECOSAR also assigns a (chemical functional group) classification, which can be seen as an indication of a specific Mode of Action (often a specific reactivity, e.g. epoxides, or receptor interaction, e.g. Esters, phosphate).
- **Toxicity Estimation Software Tool (T.E.S.T.)** from US EPA, version 5.1.2, yielding acute toxicity estimates for one fish species, the fathead Minnow (*Pimephales promelas*), one crustacean, (*Daphnia magna*) and one ciliophore (*Tetrahymena pyriformis*) which is used as the third species where often algae species are used. Software, manuals and method descriptions can be found at <https://www.epa.gov/comptox-tools/toxicity-estimation-software-tool-test>.
- **Danish QSAR models** from the Danish Food Institute (DTU), having 3 models (two models using the same database but different QSAR development software (Leadscope and SciQSAR software),

and a battery model that is the consensus model of the first two models). These models yield acute toxicity estimates for one fish (*Pimephales promelas*), one crustacean (*Daphnia magna*) and one algae (*Pseudokirchneriella s.*). The results from the QSAR models are online available from the Danish QSAR Database at <https://qsar.food.dtu.dk/> and in the database also extensive Model documentation is available.

- **VEGA QSAR Application** developed by the Instituto Mario Negri, Italy, giving 7 different acute and one chronic fish models, 4 acute and one chronic daphnid model and 2 acute and one chronic algae model. The QSAR application implementing these models and documentation are available as stand-application from <https://www.vegahub.eu/portfolio-item/vega-qsar/>. The latest version 1.1.5 (October 2024) has been applied. The list of individual ecotoxicity models run from withing the VEGA QSAR Application software is:
 - Fish Acute (LC50) Toxicity classification (SarPy/IRFMN) (version 1.0.2)
 - Fish Acute (LC50) Toxicity model (KNN/Read-Across) (version 1.0.0)
 - Fish Acute (LC50) Toxicity model (NIC) (version 1.0.0)
 - Fish Acute (LC50) Toxicity model (IRFMN) (version 1.0.0)
 - Fish Acute (LC50) Toxicity model (IRFMN/Combase) (version 1.0.0)
 - Fish Chronic (NOEC) Toxicity model (IRFMN) (version 1.0.0)
 - Fathead Minnow LC50 96h (EPA) (version 1.0.7)
 - Fathead Minnow LC50 model (KNN/IRFMN) (version 1.1.0)
 - Guppy LC50 model (KNN/IRFMN) (version 1.1.0)
 - Daphnia Magna LC50 48h (EPA) (version 1.0.7)
 - Daphnia Magna LC50 48h (DEMETRA) (version 1.0.4)
 - Daphnia Magna Acute (EC50) Toxicity model (IRFMN) (version 1.0.0)
 - Daphnia Magna Acute (EC50) Toxicity model (IRFMN/Combase) (version 1.0.0)
 - Daphnia Magna Chronic (NOEC) Toxicity model (IRFMN) (version 1.0.0)
 - Algae Acute (EC50) Toxicity model (IRFMN) (version 1.0.0)
 - Algae Acute (EC50) Toxicity model (ProtoQSAR/Combase) (version 1.0.0)
 - Algae Chronic (NOEC) Toxicity model (IRFMN) (version 1.0.0)
 - Algae Classification Toxicity model (ProtoQSAR/Combase) (version 1.0.0)

Furthermore, Mode of Action information is predicted by the following individual models:

- MOA toxicity classification (EPA T.E.S.T.) (version 1.0.0)
- MoA Classification (IRFMN) (version 1.0.0)
- Verhaar classification (TOXTREE) (version 1.0.0)

As can be seen from this list, the QSAR models from EPA T.E.S.T. are also reproduced by the VEGA QSAR Application. We have kept the results in the total overview of predictions, as the interpretation procedure (using the lowest predicted ecotoxicity value as the PNEC or PoD for ecotoxicity risk assessment) is not sensitive to duplication.

Furthermore, most models (ECOSAR, TEST and VEGA models) indicate the presence of experimental data (as part of the QSAR model training set). Instead of using the experimental data, we have used

only *predicted* values, in order for this assessment step to treat all SURPASS case study (CS) components equally. Of course available experimental data on ecotoxicity would need to be taken into account (and can override QSAR model predictions) for individual evaluation of CS compounds. For example case study 2 substance CS2_S01 Bisphenol A, CAS 80-05-7, is a substance for which a lot of experimental data is available (as well as detailed risk assessment reports in e.g. the EU REACH Annex XV dossier supporting the designation of bisphenol A as a Substance of Very High Concern (SVHC). If experimental data is available for a substance, this can be found in the results given in the output of the QSAR models (Appendix and Zenodo).

2.2 Selection of substances

The required information for QSAR modelling was not available for all ingredients of all case studies. The three case studies focus on plastic materials, therefore some of the ingredients are plastic pellets, which cannot be assessed with QSAR models. For all QSAR models (section 2.1), the input is a distinct chemical structure, of organic small molecules. Polymer structures, inorganic structures, or mixtures cannot be processed by the QSARs. As the investigated QSAR models are based on datasets of toxicity test data for small organic molecules, they are not able to extrapolate/predict the toxicity of polymers, mixtures, inorganics, metal or metal-organic compounds, nanomaterials, proteins etc.

Therefore, for each CS substance we had to determine a single chemical structure that was most representative of the case study substance. Sometimes the chemical structures are ingredients in the production process that are reactive or consumed (e.g. monomers). Only those case study substances that were also tested as such, and for which the chemical identity was not deemed confidential could be used for generating QSAR results.

The input for all models existed of a SMILES code (Simplified Molecular Input Line Entry System), a way to code chemical structure information into a single ASCII string. An example of the SMILES is given for a non-confidential ingredient from Case Study 1, ingredient 8 (disulfide):

Surpass ID	Name	CAS-registry nr.	SMILES	STRUCTURE
CS1_08	Disulfide	1892-29-1	S(SCCO)CCO	

The full lists of SURPASS identifiers of the substances for which QSAR results have been generated is given in section 4.1. All individual QSAR results are given in the Appendix to this Deliverable. The identity of some of the chemicals is considered confidential business information, therefore for these chemicals (potentially) identifying information (CAS number, name, SMILES, and experimental properties, and any information that could be used to reconstruct identifying information when combined with the QSAR results) are left out of the results. For those CS substances that were a mixture of components, all components for which a single organic structure could be defined were submitted to the QSAR models, and the lowest PNEC derived from the aquatic toxicity estimates was used. This is an overestimation of the hazard of these mixtures, as the assumption is now 100% of the mixture is made up of the most toxic component. However, no information on the individual concentrations/fractions of the components in the CS substances was available. If that information is

available (e.g. CSX.X is a mixture of two components A – 35% and B - 65%), those fractions can be used to calculate a compound toxicity – e.g. the NOEC/PNEC of the mixture. Without this information, the worst case approach (most toxic approach) is to assume the mixture is as toxic as its most toxic component (lowest PNEC).

2.2.1 Ingredients, intentionally added substances (IAS)

Case study 1

Case study 1 focussed on new recyclable-by-design bio-sourced polyurethane resins (PU) with enhanced vitrimer properties to replace polyvinyl chloride (PVC) for window frames. Different routes were defined, based on either fossil-based or bio-based PU and each with the option for recycling using catalysts (as tested by CEA) or disulfide (as tested by LEITAT). For 5 ingredients used in case study 1 (CS1) specific chemical structures could be defined suitable for the selected ecotox QSAR models. They either describe the ingredient, or (some) components in the ingredient. These ingredients are highlighted in green in Table 2.2-1. Some ingredients could be defined, but were unsuitable for the QSARs, like Bi-cat, a bismuth containing ingredient. The applied QSARs are not suited for metallo-organic substances. One of the ingredients was Niox Catalyst, a mixture for which 4 individual components could be defined as QSAR suitable single chemical structures.

Case study 2

Case study 2 focussed on new fire-resistant recyclable epoxy-vitrimer based composites integrating non-releasable fire-retardancy moieties, as alternative to metal for the train structure. For these composites 3 groups of ingredients could be defined: hardeners, resins and flame retardants. The resins were the same for all production routes. The reference route was based on MDA as a hardener and TCPP as a flame retardant. Alternative hardeners and flame retardants made the alternative production routes. The resins and flame retardants are together referred to as “A-Parts”. The composition of the A-parts was so not sufficiently defined to allow for QSAR application to the components. The three hardeners MDA, 4-AFD and 2-AFD were single chemical structures that could be used for QSAR predictions. In addition, leachates from composites with different flame retardants but the same hardener (4-AFD) were available. In total 8 components – 4 flame retardant related components identified in the leachates, and 4 impurities expected to be present as NIAS but undetected – were defined for QSAR predictions.

Case study 3

The third case study focussed on MultiNanoLayered (MNL) films optimizing their composition and compatibilizer content to make films efficient and recyclable, replacing current multi-layers films that today face uncertainty in recycling with respect to partially challenging designs and compositions, or lack of sorting and dedicated processing. The reference product was a commercially produced MNL, consisting of PO, PA and compatibilizer. Alternative products consisted of other plastic materials, more layers or did not contain compatibilizer. All ingredients for case study 3 (CS3) were pellets, which were not sufficiently specified to be able to run QSAR models for individual components in the pellets. Migration samples in 95% ethanol (referred to in the Tabel as E95) were provided. 8 different components from the 95% ethanol migration samples were defined and QSAR predictions were generated.

Table 2.2-1: Overview of the substances tested for each of the case studies. Substances for which single chemical structures could be defined as input for QSARs are highlighted in green.

	Case Study 1	Case Study 2	Case Study 3
Priority 1	Bi-Cat Cystamine THEED Disulfide Polyol I Polyol A Polyol B Polyol C Polyol D	AP-CL AP1 AP2 AP3 AP4 MDA 4-AFD 2-AFD	PO/PA/compat 11 B PE/compat/PA 65 B PE/EVOH 129 B PE/compat/EVOH 129 B PO/PA/compat 11 E95 PE/compat/PA 65 E95 PE/EVOH 129 E95 PE/compat/EVOH 129 E95
Priority 2	Diisocyanate Niax Catalyst Niax Silicon FR CROS 484	Leach-TCPP Leach-SP1 Leach-SP2 Leach-SP3 Leach-SP4	

2.2.2 Non-intentionally added substances

In addition to the ingredients used in the production process, other potential hazardous substances are those that could be:

- Released during production or use;
- Formed during the production process;
- Released during the recycling phase.

Therefore, hazard evaluation of these substances should be included in case human or environmental exposure is relevant. Specifically for CS2 and CS3, information on substances released during production or use was available (step 7 of Figure 2.2-1: Sources and categories of NIAS ("Chemicals in Plastics - a technical report" of United Nations Environment programme 2023).). These substances could have been intentionally added (IAS) or non-intentionally added substances (NIAS).

The concept of NIAS was introduced through regulations related to food contact applications. For example, the Regulation EU 10/2011 for plastics food contact materials, the following NIAS definition is provided as "Non-intentionally added substance" means an impurity in the substances used or a reaction intermediate formed during the production process or a decomposition or reaction product.

The United Nations Environment programme 2023 reported the subcategories of NIAS Figure 2.2-1: Sources and categories of NIAS ("Chemicals in Plastics - a technical report" of United Nations Environment programme 2023).

Figure 2.2-1: Sources and categories of NIAS ("Chemicals in Plastics - a technical report" of United Nations Environment programme 2023).

The strategy associated with this objective involves three steps (Nerín et al. 2022):

- Step 1: Detect unknown substance (non-exhaustive list).
- Step 2: Identify unknown substance (non-exhaustive list).
- Step 3: Formulate a hypothesis on the NIAS or IAS category of the identified substance of interest (Groh et al. 2019).

For CS2 information was available on NIAS coming from the ingredients used and was included in QSAR modelling. For CS3, chemical analysis of migration samples was conducted to identify IAS and NIAS. This information was used for QSAR modelling and exposure modelling. The focus was on the substances for which a Cas No can be identified, so classes of compounds were excluded.

NIAS for CS2

Four specific NIAS are identified related to the flame retardant used (CS2_45, 46, 47 and 48) and furthermore 4 separate *suspected* NIAS (undetected, but expected impurities in the ingredients) were identified, labeled CS2_41, 42, 43 and 44).

NIAS for CS3

The study of NIAS for CS3 was conducted as part of sub-task 4.2 and was presented in D4.2 submitted in M33.

Currently, this strategy of NIAS identification is not exhaustive due to the limitations of existing analytical techniques (detection limits, identification limits, etc.). Screening analysis can be conducted for unpredicted compounds but also detects predicted compounds as well as IAS.

The objective is to take in account the step of use (consumer of food in contact with MNL film).

The identification of NIAS is performed with migration test on several MNL films (reference and SSbD solutions mLLDPE/compatibilizer/PA) according to regulation 10/2011/EC.

The following methodology is applied:

- Migration test of MNL film: 10 days at 60°C (Application: long-term contact between the food and the packaging) in 95% ethanol simulant (the most stringent for PE/PA product).
- Chemical analysis of simulant by gas chromatography mass spectrometry (GC-MS).

3. Relation between physical chemical properties and hazard

Physical chemical properties of chemicals could explain (some of their) hazardous effects. Screening for potential hazardous effects in an early stage is relatively easy and therefore ideal in a SSbD approach for hazard assessment. Essentially two approaches can be followed, the first is making use of existing databases of relations between physical chemical properties and hazard. Physical chemical properties of substances with unknown hazard are used to obtain information on their hazard. The second approach is to correlate physical chemical properties with the results of in vitro assays. Whereas the first approach can be done in an early stage of the production process, the second approach requires substance specific information and could be done at a later stage. In SURPASS we intended to use the second approach.

Several QSAR models for the ecotoxicological hazard (LC/E50 and NOEC) estimation are using the (known) relationship between physico-chemical properties and aquatic toxicity. For substances without a specific toxicity mechanism of action effect (mortality) is considered to be caused by partitioning of a substance in the phospholipid bilayer of the cell membranes of the organisms (fish, daphnids, algae), thereby disturbing the cell membrane processes, eventually leading to (cell) death. It has been known for a long time that there is a strong correlation between the water-lipid partitioning and aquatic toxicity for specific groups of (mostly inert) organic chemicals. For example the ECOSAR QSAR models (US EPA) exploits this relationship by using the octanol-water partitioning constant (log Kow) to predict aquatic toxicity for homologous groups of chemicals. Details on the methodology can be found in the model documentation (<https://www.epa.gov/system/files/documents/2022-03/methodology-document-v.2.2.pdf>).

This linear relationship between log Kow and log toxicity for different chemical functional groups is illustrated by the figure below (Figure 2.2-2), taken from the ECOSAR model documentation:

Figure 2.2-2 Plot of Octanol-Water Partition Coefficient vs. Fish Acute Toxicity for Several Chemical Classes.

Reference: Octanol-Water Partition Coefficient ($\log P$) Cut-Offs and Predicted Magnitude of Fish Acute Toxicity (expressed as median lethal concentration, LC_{50}) for Several Chemical Classes Using Equations from: Clements, R.G., Nabholz, J.V., ECOSAR: A Computer Program for Estimating the Ecotoxicity of Industrial Chemicals Based on Structure Activity Relationships, U.S. EPA, OPPT (7403), Technical Publication, 748-R-93-002, 1994.

It is also well-known that water solubility will correlate strongly with the octanol-water partition coefficient. Therefore, using the QSAR generated hazard information to explore the relationships between physicochemical properties and hazard would likely only reproduce the causal relationships that were used to derive the QSAR model, and hence would not be informative. It will only reproduce the relationship that was used to generate the model, not indicate any empirical (deviation from) relationships as it is not based on experimental observations.

To relate physical chemical properties with the results of in vitro assays (D4.3) a selection of substances needed to be made. Several ingredients were tested as a mixture only, for example the polyols (CS1), the A-parts (CS2) and the migration samples (CS3). No physical chemical information is available for these specific mixtures. Excluding these mixtures, resulted in 4 substances for CS1 (Bi-Cat, cystamine, THEED and disulfide) and 3 substances for CS2 (MDA, 4-AFD and 2-AFD), of which the CS1 substances were second priority for in vitro testing, meaning that there was no or limited data available.

For these 7 substances, information on their physical chemical properties was searched in pubchem, Reach dossier and the SDS. Many physical chemical parameters were not available (Table 3.1-1).

Table 3.1-1: Physical chemical properties for the 7 substances from CS1 and CS2.

Group of substances	Catalysts	Catalysts	Catalysts	Disulfide	Hardeners	Hardeners	Hardeners
Substance name	Bismuth neodecanoate	Cystamine	N,N,N',N'-Tetrakis(2-hydroxyethyl) ethylenediamine	2-hydroxyethyl disulfide	4,4'-Diaminodiphenylmethane	4-Aminophenyl disulfide	2-Aminophenyl disulfide
SURPASS Code	CS1_16	CS1_26	CS1_18	CS1_08	CS2_14	CS2_02	CS2_15
CAS No(s)	34364-26-6	56-17-7	140-07-8	1892-29-1	101-77-9	722-27-0	1141-88-4
Abbreviation	Bi-Cat	Cystamine	THEED	Disulfide	MDA	4-AFD	2-AFD
Molecular weight	722.75	225.2	236.31	154.25	198.26	248.37	248.37
Boiling point	300 °C	NA	280 °C	158 - 163 °C at 4,7 hPa	398°C +/- 5°C	447 °C	NA
Melting point	-50 - 0 °C	217 - 220 °C (decomposes)	NA	25 - 27 °C	90°C - 92°C	77°C - 78°C	91°C - 92°C
Flash point	Not applicable	NA	99 °C	112 °C	220°C	224,2 °C	NA
Solubility (water 25°C)	1.87 g/l at 21.5 °C	NA	NA	>1000 g/l at 20 °C	1010 mg/L at 25°C	NA	14 mg/L at 20°C
Density	1.145 g/cm ³ at 25 °C	NA	1.1 g/cm ³ at 20 °C	1.261 g/cm ³ at 25 °C	1,15 g/cm ³ at 20°C	NA	NA
Vapour pressure	NA	NA	NA	0.47 hPa at 135 °C	0.00025 Pa at 25°C	NA	NA
Log P (or log Kow)	NA	NA	NA	0.3	1,55 at 25°C	NA	3.05
Dissoociation constants (pKa)	NA	NA	NA	NA	4.96 at 20°C	NA	NA
Viscosity	NA	NA	NA	NA	8.3 cP at 100°C	NA	NA
Source of information	SDS & REACH data	SDS	SDS	SDS & REACH data	REACH data / PubChem	SDS	SDS

NA = not available

Considering the limited number of substances and the data gaps for these substances, we decided not to proceed with correlating physical chemical properties to hazard information. In the context of hazard assessment in an SSbD approach, we advise to explore this path at an early stage of the production process, and making use of existing data bases with information on relations between physical chemical properties and hazard properties.

4. Description of the work and main achievements

4.1 QSAR modelling results

In the Appendix all individual model results are given. For some models/CS substances results were judged to be outside the known applicability domain and no result was generated by the software, meaning that not for all Case Study chemicals there will be a predicted toxicity result from all models for all the CS substances. Whether a model is thought to be able to generate a reliable prediction for

a specific substance depends on the chemical structure and whether sufficiently closely related chemical structures (similar in terms of chemical functionalities and/or physicochemical properties) are present in the datasets used to derive the QSAR models.

In the following sections the result from the data interpretation algorithm for deriving the PNEC / PoD aquatic toxicity from multiple predictions is given. This derived PNEC is a single indicator for aquatic toxicity for each CS compound, and can be used as the basis for the SURPASS scores. The predictions from the various QSAR models per compound are interpreted as follows to generate a single PNEC / PoD per CS compound:

$$\text{PNEC} = \text{lowest predicted value of} \\ (\text{QSARchronic results}) \text{ OR } (\text{QSARacute results} / 10), \text{ in mg/L}$$

For each Case study substance it is indicated which specific QSAR model and for which aquatic species the lowest predicted no-effect concentration was generated. Furthermore, as not all QSAR models perform identical checks regarding the applicability domain, we manually check whether the QSAR based PNEC is actually below the (predicted) water solubility (QSAR results for predicting water solubility are given in the tab ECOSAR v2.2 of the Appendix). Furthermore, the bioavailability / time-scale limitation that is applied by the ECOSAR v2.2 model using the octanol-water partition coefficient (log Kow) is applied to all the acute toxicity predictions – indicating that no acute effect can be expected at the time scale of the acute toxicity tests (maximum test duration: 96 hours) if the estimated log Kow is larger than 5.0. For all chronic toxicity test predictions, it is indicated that no chronic effects can be expected if the log Kow is above 8.0.

4.1.1 CS1

Five intentionally added substances of CS1 could be characterized as a single small organic chemical – suitable for QSAR model prediction. The identity of the individual components is given in the Appendix, when the identity of the component was not confidential. For confidential ingredients the chemical structure has been communicated to RIVM to allow for QSAR predictions to be generated, but only the results of the QSAR models are given in the Appendix.

The result of the selection of the ecotoxicological PoD / PNEC for these five compounds is given below (

Table 4.1-1).

Table 4.1-1: Result of the selection of the ecotoxicological PoD / PNEC for the 5 CS1 compounds.

SURPASS chemical identifier	Name	LOWEST PNEC ACUTE/10 CHRONIC in mg/L	or MODEL / SPECIES / DURATION giving LOWEST toxicity prediction?
CS1_04	Polyol D	1.66E+00	VEGA IRFMN - ALGAE ACUTE
CS1_08	Disulfide	1.14E-01	VEGA IRFMN/Combase - DAPHNIA ACUTE
CS1_26	Cystamine	5.39E-03	VEGA IRFMN/Combase - DAPHNIA ACUTE
CS1_18	THEED	1.01E-01	VEGA IRFMN/Combase - DAPHNIA ACUTE
CS1_20-1	Niax Catalyst	1.80E-01	VEGA IRFMN/Combase - DAPHNIA ACUTE
CS1_20-2	Niax Catalyst	4.87E-01	VEGA NIC - FISH ACUTE
CS1_20-3	Niax Catalyst	1.61E+00	VEGA DEMETRA - DAPHNIA ACUTE
CS1_20-4	Niax Catalyst	2.87E-01	VEGA IRFMN - DAPHNIA CHRONIC

For CS1_20 four different single component structures were identified that are present in the product Niax Catalyst (CS1_20-1, CS1_20-2, CS1_20-3 and CS1_20-4). QSAR results were generated for all four components of this intentionally added substance. Without information on the individual fractions of these components, the lowest predicted toxicity value (for component CS1_20-1) has to be considered worst case representative of the whole mixture CS1_20. It can already be seen that not one single QSAR model, or one species, always is giving the lowest toxicity prediction, indicating the need for using multiple QSAR models, for multiple endpoints and species. The model/species/duration combination that leads to the most sensitive (most toxic) QSAR prediction is discussed for the whole group of QSAR prediction (total of 27 individual component predictions) in section 4.2.4.

4.1.2 CS2

Three intentionally added substances were characterized as suitable structures for QSAR application in CS2. The detailed results of the individual QSAR predictions are given in Appendix and Zenodo, the result of the data interpretation procedure giving the single QSAR based PNEC-value is given below (Table 4.1-2).

Table 4.1-2: Result of the selection of the ecotoxicological PoD / PNEC for the 3 CS2 compounds.

SURPASS chemical identifier	Name	LOWEST PNEC ACUTE/10 or CHRONIC in mg/L	MODEL / SPECIES / DURATION giving LOWEST toxicity prediction?
CS2_02	4-Aminophenyl disulfide	7.90E-04	DTU SciQSAR Daphnia magna 48hr EC50
CS2_14	4,4'-Diaminodiphenylmethane	1.33E-02	ECOSAR Daphnid CHRONIC NOEC
CS2_15	2-Aminophenyl disulfide	8.16E-04	DTU SciQSAR Daphnia magna 48hr EC50

4.1.3 CS3

In CS3 only leachates from products have been tested. Substances that were detected and identified in the leachates, were also used to generate QSAR model predictions, these are discussed in section 4.2 on Non Intentionally Added Substances (NIAS).

4.2 NIAS

4.2.1 CS1

No NIAS were identified for CS1.

4.2.2 CS2

Four substances were detected and identified in the leachate of CS2. The QSAR based PNEC estimation for these four substances yielded the following results (

Table 4.1-1).

Table 4.2-1: Result of the selection of the ecotoxicological PoD / PNEC for the 4 CS2 NIAS

SURPASS chemical identifier	Name	LOWEST PNEC ACUTE/10 or CHRONIC in mg/L	MODEL / SPECIES / DURATION giving LOWEST toxicity prediction?
CS2_41	2-Propanol, 1-chloro-	2.75E-02	VEGA PROTOQSAR/ Combase - ALGAE ACUTE
CS2_42	2-Propanol, 1-chloro-, phosphate (3:1)	4.40E-05	VEGA DEMETRA - DAPHNIA ACUTE
CS2_43	Bis(1-chloro-2-propyl) (3-chloro-1-propyl)phosphate	1.10E-04	VEGA DEMETRA - DAPHNIA ACUTE
CS2_44	Bis(3-chloro-1-propyl) (1-chloro-2-propyl)phosphate	1.05E-04	VEGA DEMETRA - DAPHNIA ACUTE

Additionally, there are 4 suspected NIAS identified in CS2. The QSAR based PNEC estimation for these four substances yielded the following results (Table 4.2-2).

Table 4.2-2: Result of the selection of the ecotoxicological PoD / PNEC for the 4 suspected CS2 NIAS.

SURPASS chemical identifier	Name	LOWEST PNEC ACUTE/10 or CHRONIC in mg/L	MODEL / SPECIES / DURATION giving LOWEST toxicity prediction?
CS2_45	Bisphenol A	1.90E-02	VEGA IRFMN/Combase - DAPHNIA ACUTE
CS2_46	4-aminothiophenol	5.09E-04	VEGA IRFMN - ALGAE ACUTE
CS2_47	Formaldehyde	5.66E-02	ECOSAR Daphnid CHRONIC NOEC
CS2_48	Aniline	1.10E-02	ECOSAR Daphnid CHRONIC NOEC

See Appendix and Zenodo for the individual detailed QSAR results.

4.2.3 CS3

The identification results in Table 4.2-3 demonstrate the presence of organic NIAS in 95% ethanol simulants after contact with MNL films.

Table 4.2-3: NIAS in migration test (MT) on 95% ethanol after contact with mLLDPE/PA MNL films.

Identification substance	CAS number	Detected substance (X)			
		Reference PO/compatibilizer/PA 11 layers	MNL film mLLDPE/compatibilizer/PA 65 layers 15wt% compatibilizer	MNL film mLLDPE/compatibilizer/PA 129 layers 7,5wt% compatibilizer	MNL film mLLDPE/PA 129 layers
Caprolactam	105-60-2	(X)	(X)	(X)	(X)
Undecanoic acid	112-37-8	(X)			
Amide	/	(X)			
2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol	96-76-4			(X)	(X)
No identified	/	(X)	(X)	(X)	(X)
Tris(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl) phosphate	95906-11-9	(X)	(X)	(X)	(X)

The NIAS are determined based on existing bibliographic data. These are substances that are not usually intentionally added to PE, PA matrices or that are not authorized under EU Regulation 10/2011/EC (the polymer grades used are food-grade and therefore comply with the requirements of this regulation).

For example:

- The substance with CAS No. 95906-11-9 is a degradation product of the antioxidant Irgafos 168. This antioxidant is commonly used in the composition of polyolefins such as polyethylene. It is not compliant with Regulation 10/2011/EC.
- The substance with CAS No. 96-76-4 is not compliant with Regulation 10/2011/EC. It is a degradation or transformation product. It is detected in configurations with a high number of layers (>129 layers).

We looked into the hazards associated with these NIAS through the website of the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA). They are presented in the following Table 4.2-4 except for the two NIAS in blank cell in Table 4.2-3 because no precise identification is done.

Table 4.2-4: Hazard of NIAS detected following ECHA website.

Identification substance (SURPASS_ID)	CAS number	Hazard (ECHA website)	
Caprolactam (CS3_17)	105-60-2	<p>Substance identity</p> <p>EC / List no.: 203-313-2</p> <p>CAS no.: 105-60-2</p> <p>Mol. formula: C₆H₁₁NO</p> <p><i>Warning!</i> According to the harmonised classification and labelling (CLP00) approved by the European Union, this substance is harmful if swallowed, causes serious eye irritation, is harmful if inhaled, causes skin irritation and may cause respiratory irritation.</p>	
Undecanoic acid (CS3_18)	112-37-8	<p>Substance identity</p> <p>EC / List no.: 203-964-2</p> <p>CAS no.: 112-37-8</p> <p>Mol. formula: C₁₁H₂₂O₂</p>	<p>Hazard classification & labelling</p> <p><i>Warning!</i> According to the classification provided by companies to ECHA in REACH registrations this substance causes skin irritation.</p>
2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol (CS3_19)	96-76-4	<p>Substance identity</p> <p>EC / List no.: 202-532-0</p> <p>CAS no.: 96-76-4</p> <p>Mol. formula: C₁₄H₂₂O</p> <p>Under assessment as Endocrine Disrupting</p> <p>More details</p>	
Tris(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl) phosphate (CS3_20)	95906-11-9	No data available	

The four NIAS in green in Table 4.2-4 are quantified in order to have their level of exposition. The reagent of each substance was bought by IPC and the quantification is performed by GC-MS.

The results for quantification (on ppm) of this 4 NIAS are done in Table 4.2-5.

The two others NIAS in blank cell in Table 4.2-3, can't be quantify because no precise identification is done.

Table 4.2-5: NIAS quantification on 95% ethanol (ppm).

NIAS identified		Reference film PO/compatibilizer/PA 11 layers	MNL film mLLDPE/compatibilizer/PA 65 layers 15wt% compatibilizer	MNL film mLLDPE/compatibilizer/PA 129 layers 7,5wt% compatibilizer	MNL film mLLDPE/PA 129 layers
Name	Number CAS				
Caprolactam (CS3_17)	105-60-2	3,4	0,6	1,4	0,3
Undecanoic acid (CS3_18)	112-37-8	< 0.3 ppm	Not identified	Not identified	Not identified
2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol (CS3_19)	96-76-4	0,07	0,03	0,33	0,04
Tris(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl) phosphate (CS3_20)	95906-11-9	1,5	4,4	9,3	11,5

QSAR modelling

Several substances are detected on the 95% ethanol after contact. They are listed in Table 4.2-3. The four identified NIAS in green have also been used to generate QSAR predictions of ecotoxicological hazard. These are numbered CS3_17 – caprolactam, CS3_18 – undecanoic acid, CS3_19 – 2,4-di-tert-butylphenol, and CS3-20 - tris(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl) phosphate in the QSAR results in Appendix and Zenodo and in the table below. Additionally in total four more individual compounds were identified in the leachate; two belonging to the “amide” group in Table 4.2-3, namely CS3_21 oleamide and CS3_22 erucamide; and two substances belonging to the No identified group – being flame retardants, namely CS3_23 irgafos-168 and CS3_24 irganox-1076. The QSAR based PNEC estimation for these eight substances yielded the following results in Table 4.2-6:

Table 4.2-6: Result of the selection of the ecotoxicological PoD / PNEC for the CS3 NIAs.

SURPASS chemical identifier	Name	LOWEST PNEC ACUTE/10 or CHRONIC in mg/L	MODEL / SPECIES / DURATION giving LOWEST toxicity prediction?
CS3_17	Caprolactam	2.97E-01	VEGA IRFMN/Combase - DAPHNIA ACUTE
CS3_18	Undecanoic acid	4.90E-02	VEGA NIC - FISH ACUTE
CS3_21	Oleamide	1.33E-03	ECOSAR FISH CHRONIC NOEC
CS3_22	Erucamide	No effects at any dose	VEGA IRFMN/Combase FISH ACUTE
CS3_19	2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol	1.11E-02	VEGA IRFMN/Combase - DAPHNIA ACUTE
CS3_23	Irgafos 168	No effects at any dose	VEGA IRFMN/Combase - DAPHNIA ACUTE
CS3_24	Irganox 1076	No effects at any dose	EPA - FATHEAD MINNOW ACUTE
CS3_20	Tris(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl) phosphate	No effects at any dose	VEGA IRFMN/Combase - DAPHNIA ACUTE

* Substances highlighted indicate PNEC prediction that are well above the estimated maximum water solubility of the substance, Oleamide is predicted to be too insoluble in water to give acute effects (log Kow > 5). The 4 substances indicated in red have predicted log Kow values > 8 and predicted water solubilities that are below the QSAR derived PNEC values. This means that even though the predicted PNEC would be very low (highly toxic), it is highly unlikely that any effect will be observed due to exposure to these substances.

It is very important with these results to realize the chemical structures of CS3_21 and 22 (oleamide and erucamide) as well as CS3_23, 24 and 20 are expected to have extremely low water solubilities, leading to «outside applicability domain» calls from several QSAR models. For those models resulting in extremely low No Effect Concentrations (from 0.7 microgram/L for oleamide down to 2.6 femtogram/L for irgafos 167) the results have to be distrusted as these are extreme extrapolations and apparently the applicability domain check for these models did not look critically at bioavailability issues. For example, the ECOSAR models indicate that for four substances (CS3_06, 09, 10 and 11) water solubility is expected to be very well below the predicted NOECs. Therefore, it is very unlikely to expect any toxicity effect up to the maximum water solubility of these compounds, both for acute as well as chronic effects. For CS3_21 (oleamide) the water solubility at the duration of the acute tox testing is considered too low to expect any acute toxicity effects (log Kow > 5), but chronic effects might still occur. For example, the predicted (lowest) No effect concentration of oleamide would be

0.707 microgram/L, based on a prediction of acute toxicity effects at 7.07 micrograms/L from the VEGA IRFMN/Combase - FISH ACUTE model. However, this prediction (7.07 mg/L) is above the predicted water solubility for oleamide of 4.6 micrograms/L. The lowest chronic toxicity NOEC prediction would be 1.33 microgram/L (ECOSAR Fish chronic toxicity model) which is below (but close to) the predicted maximum water solubility of 4.6 microgram/L.

The predicted no effect concentration for CS3_23 - irgafos 167, is 2.6×10^{-9} mg/L = 2.6 femtogram/L. This could be mistakenly seen as extremely toxic, but the predicted maximum water solubility is actually a factor 100.000 lower at 2.9×10^{-14} mg/L. It is therefore very unlikely that the substance can exert any toxic effect in the aquatic compartment.

In general, QSAR models are not suitable for this kind of very insoluble, not biologically available substances, even if they do generate a quantitative prediction. If an individual QSAR model indicates such a (low reliability) result, as e.g. coming from the VEGA models for acute toxicity for CS3_22, 23, and 20, and the USEPA T.E.S.T. acute fathead minnow model for CS3_24, it is extremely unlikely that similar non-water soluble substances were part of the training datasets of these QSARS, therefore the predictions represent extreme extrapolations. We have applied the bioavailability/solubility criteria as derived for the ECOSAR v2.2 model also to the outcomes of other QSAR models for ecotoxicity. Therefore no predictions for CS3_22,23, 24 and 20 are given (and colored in red) in table, as their theoretical ecotox hazard values are NOT necessarily an indication of any risk, due to the very low (expected) bioavailability of these substances.

In general, for other purposes than screening/prioritizing/comparing SSbD routes and substances (e.g. risk assessment), the reliability of the generated QSAR based PNEC values would need to be scrutinized on a case by case basis, by going back to the individual predictions and the details on e.g. applicability domain calls, using information on most similar substances in the training datasets and taking into account data on bioavailability, and possibly existing (other) experimental toxicity data, in order to substantiate the hazard.

ConsExpo

The ConsExpo Tool (<https://consexpweb.nl/my.policy>) is a software package developed by the RIVM (Dutch National Institute for Public Health and the Environment). It is used to estimate the exposure of consumers to chemical substances through various scenarios involving the use of everyday consumer products (cosmetics, cleaning products, paints, etc.).

ConsExpo is designed to :

- Model exposure by inhalation, ingestion or skin contact.
- Provide quantification of exposure in realistic or conservative scenarios.
- Be used by regulatory authorities, researchers and industry.

For CS3, MNL film for food contact applications, the exposure route taken into account is oral exposure (ingestion).

ConsExpo provides a Migration from Packaging model. Exposure is calculated as the quantity potentially taken up per kg body weight and the actual dose (amount absorbed per kg body weight), using a user-provided absorption fraction.

This exposure model estimates the intake of substances migrating from food packaging materials into food. Migration is calculated based on the concentration of the substance in the packaging, the contact area between the packaging and the food, and the migration rate.

Oral exposure is then derived by assuming the substance is evenly distributed throughout the food, meaning that intake is proportional to the fraction of the packaged food that is consumed.

The parameters required to perform this type of exposure assessment include:

- Substance concentration: the concentration of the substance in the packaging material.
- Package thickness: the thickness of the packaging material.
- Contact area: the surface area in contact between the packaging and the food.
- Packaged amount: the quantity of food contained within the packaging.
- Ingested amount: the portion of the packaged food that is actually consumed.

For CS3, we have the amount of migrating substance in simulant by performing migration tests (see Table 4.2-5) but not the concentration of the substance in packaging material. Data are present in Table 4.2 5. The Migration from Packaging model of ConsExpo is not applicable with data available.

For this purpose, and based on the standard EU method for assessing exposure to chemicals present in food contact materials and the risks they pose, the following default values are used:

- A person with a body weight (bw) of 60 kg consumes 1 kg of food per day that has been in contact with 6 dm² of the examined food contact material. (see EFSA document: [Recent developments in the risk assessment of chemicals in food and their potential impact on the safety assessment of substances used in food contact materials.](#))
- If the migration test was carried out proportionally, using 6 dm²/kg (contact surface / mass of the food simulant), the concentration measured in the simulant can be used as the modeled amount of the substance present in the food. It's applicable for samples of migration tests.

From the (modelled=calculated) concentration of the chemical in the food simulant, it is possible to estimate external oral or dietary exposure using the “direct product contact” model based on the following equation.

$\text{Oral Exposure [mg/kg bw/day]} = \text{modelled concentration [mg/kg]} \times 1 \text{ [kg/day]} / 60 \text{ [kg bw]}$
--

Exposure was assessed for each NIAS from CS3, based on the highest content obtained in the 95% ethanol simulant among the four tested film samples.

The results of the oral exposure assessment, in mg/kg bw/day, calculated in this way are presented in the Table 4.2-7. It corresponds to the amount that can potentially be absorbed per kg body weight during one day.

Table 4.2-7: Result of oral exposure assessment for CS3 NIAS by ConsExpo tool.

NIAS identified		Quantification on 95 % Ethanol simulant (mg/kg)		Data ConsExpo		
Name	Number CAS	For sample	Maximum Value	Kow (10 Log)	Mw (g/mol)	Oral exposure (mg/kg bw/day)
Caprolactam (CS3_17)	105-60-2	Reference film PO/compatibilizer/PA 11 layers	3,4	1,2	113	$5,7 \times 10^{-2}$
Undecanoic acid (CS13_18)	112-37-8		<0,3	44,2	186	$5,0 \times 10^{-3}$
2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol (CS3_19)	96-76-4	MNL film mLLDPE/compatibilizer/PA 129 layers 7,5wt% compatibilizer	0,33	51,9	206	$5,5 \times 10^{-3}$
Tris(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl) phosphate (CS3_20)	95906-11-9	MNL film mLLDPE/PA 129 layers	11,5	No available	663	$1,9 \times 10^{-1}$

Legend :

Kow [10 log] : octanol-water partition coefficient

Mw [g/mol] : Molar mass (weight average)

To determine whether this external oral exposure presents a risk, it is necessary to compare the estimated value to a health-based reference value.

We have chosen to compare it to the toxicological threshold of concern, namely the TTC (Toxicological Threshold Concentration). For example, for genotoxic carcinogens, TTC corresponds to a chronic daily exposure of $0.0025 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}/\text{day}$ (i.e., an acute toxicological threshold TA of $0.15 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ of food for a 60 kg adult consuming 1 kg of this product). This TTC threshold is sufficiently low to consider that the risk associated with exposure to unknown substances with genotoxic alert structures can be regarded as negligible.

We do not know with certainty the TTC of the 4 NIAS from CS3. We will base ourselves on the thresholds defined by EFSA for different toxicological classes of substances. The values are shown in Table 4.2-8.

Table 4.2-8 : TTC thresholds based on the assumptions of a 60 kg adult and a daily consumption of 1 kg of food

Classes / Types of Substances	Expressed in mg/kg bw/day
With structure for genotoxicity	$2,5 \times 10^{-6}$
Organophosphates and carbamates	$0,3 \times 10^{-3}$
Cramer Class III	$1,5 \times 10^{-3}$
Cramer Class II	9×10^{-3}
Cramer Class I	30×10^{-3}

If this TTC threshold is exceeded based on the oral exposure estimate made using the ConsExpo tool, it does not necessarily mean that adverse health effects will occur, but the absence of such effects can no longer be guaranteed.

We do not know the Cramer class of the 4 NIAS; we will compare the TTC thresholds with the estimated oral exposure:

- Caprolactam & tris(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl) phosphate: Its estimated oral exposure is higher than the EFSA TTC thresholds.
- Undecanoic acid & 2,4-di-tert-butylphenol: Its estimated oral exposure exceeds the EFSA TTC thresholds set for substances in Cramer Class III.

As most anthropogenic substances are considered as a Cramer class III substance, the conclusion from the comparison of the oral exposure with the TTC is that toxicological effects cannot be excluded based only on their exposure concentrations. The risk assessment needs to be refined in a next tier where substance specific toxicity information can be included.

It is also possible to compare the quantification in the 95% ethanol simulant with the specific migration limits (SMLs) defined by EU Regulation 10/2011, in the case of substances authorized under this same regulation.

This is the case for caprolactam, which is subject to an SML: we obtained a specific migration value of 3 mg/kg, whereas its SML is 60 mg/kg. Therefore, its migration level complies with the requirements of EU Regulation 10/2011 and does not pose any health risks.

For the other 3 NIAS, which are prohibited under EU Regulation 10/2011, we cannot draw conclusions regarding the risk associated with oral exposure.

4.2.4 QSAR Modelling – need for multiple models and species

Overall, for 27 single chemical structures QSAR predictions for aquatic toxicity have been generated. Looking at the most sensitive predictions that are used to generate the single compound PNEC values, it turns out that not one model, one species, or only chronic or acute/10 values are the most sensitive (most toxic). Depending on the substance any model could give the more sensitive result.

From the toxicity QSAR prediction for these 27 substances 19 times one of the daphnia models is the most sensitive, 5 times a fish model and 3 times the algae model. This is consistent with earlier analysis of experimental aquatic toxicity data submitted for the REACH legislation on industrial chemicals. In that dataset for ~87% of the chemicals the daphnia data turned out to be the most sensitive aquatic toxicity test result. This reflects the differences between the models in the dataset used to derive the model (different type of substances in the training datasets) and the different algorithms used (some models rely on correlation with log Kow or solubility, others use substructure contributions, or other descriptors). Selecting the most sensitive model/species/duration from a battery of QSAR results for determination of a PNEC is therefore good practice, and reflecting the actual practice for experimental

results in risk assessment as well, as also the most sensitive value of the tested aquatic species representing different trophic levels is used as Point of Departure for risk assessment.

Ecotoxicological chemicals risk assessment aims to protect ecosystems, so not individual species. The idea of sampling one fish, one arthropod and one plant (algae) species is to represent the diversity of species living in the aquatic environment with these three species, and hopefully protecting them by using the most sensitive species as Point of Departure. However, ideally much more species are tested, and a *Species-Sensitivity Distribution (SSD)* can be generated. This distribution allows to select a *protection level* for the whole ecosystem, typically the goal of ecotoxicological chemicals management is to protect at least 95% of all species from any effect of a chemical in the environment. Nowadays, with AI/Machine learning methods attempts are undertaken to predict not a single species toxicity value (L/EC50 or NOEC) but to predict SSDs for a wide range of species, and use the 5th percentile of such a SSD as the Point of Departure for risk assessment. Also at RIVM already promising results of such modeling exercises have been generated

However, for experience in application, use and interpretation of these newer type models is still ongoing, and results were too premature to apply these SSD models to the SURPASS Case Studies.

When looking at the QSAR models that are determining the QSAR based PNEC value for the different SURPASS substances (the model giving the lowest chronic NOEC, or the lowest acute EC50/10, it is observed that not only different species (fish/daphnid/algae) can be the basis of the QSAR derived PNEC, but it is also not one type of QSAR model that consequently gives the lowest estimate. Actually 10 different QSAR models generated the lowest PNEC for these 27 substances. For several substances the whole battery of QSAR models is quite consistent, as can be derived from looking at the difference between the lowest predicted value and the geometric mean value of all predictions, given in the Appendix for the QSAR based PNECs, the chronic and chronic QSAR prediction, and additionally also separately for the sets of fish, daphnid and algae models (acute and chronic). When looking at the QSAR based PNEC predictions, the difference between the (geometric) mean and lowest value is less than two orders of magnitude for 14 of the 23 substances (4 substances do not have a QSAR based PNEC prediction). For another 6 substances the lowest value is still less than a factor of 660 below the geometric mean of the battery of models, and for 3 substances the difference is between a factor of 1200 and 2330. When looking specifically at the substances that show this large difference between the lowest and the average model predictions it is noted that for all three the VEGA DEMETRA model for acute toxicity to daphnids is giving a much lower prediction of toxicity than the other QSAR models, and these three substances are three organophosphates. This result is due to the specific training data set used for the DEMETRA models, which are models trained on (and intended to be used for) Plant Protection Products (PPPs). It is likely that most or all organophosphate substances in the DEMETRA model training dataset are pesticide OP-esters which will be designed to have a very high toxicity to insects, and daphnids (waterfleas) are also insects. This explains the very low PNEC prediction from this model. It is based on the assumption that these organophosphates (CS2_L02, 03 and 04) will have some AChE inhibition effect – analogous to PPP organophosphates in the DEMETRA dataset. Whether the DEMETRA models or the other QSAR models are more correct, is outside the scope of this analysis. However, follow up for these substances when they would turn out to be priority substances for their (ecotoxicological) hazard, would include evaluation of evidence that these phosphates do or do not exert neurotoxicity via AChE inhibition.

5. Scoring

The method for scoring is described in D4.3. This chapter therefore focusses on scoring results of QSAR modelling.

Thresholds, to compare the effects of QSAR modelling with data from Daphnia and Zebrafish (D4.3) and to calculate a score, were based on classification limits. These classification limits are used for labelling and classification of chemicals. At or higher than 100 mg/L (for chronic effects) or 1000 mg/L (for acute effects) the substance is considered not toxic. At 10 mg/L (for chronic effects) or 100 mg/L (for acute effects), the substance is considered slightly toxic.

5.1 Case Study 1

The number of substances for which QSAR analysis could be done, was limited due to a lack of information required to run the models. Therefore, only some ingredients could be assessed and scored. A hazard score for each production route could not be calculated. The ingredient scores do, however, allow comparison of the catalysts.

The ingredient scores are shown in Table 5.1-1 and Figure 5.1-1. Generally, QSARs results in higher scores than zebrafish or daphnia. This is not surprising, as QSAR scores are based on the lowest PNEC of several species, whereas for daphnia and zebrafish the results are obviously based on a single species. This means that QSAR data can be considered more conservative.

Table 5.1-1: Ecotoxicity scoring based on QSAR models and Daphnia and Zebrafish experiments for CS1 substances.

	SSbD#0, SSbD#1, SSbD#2	SSbD#2	SSbD#1	SSbD#1	SSbD#0, SSbD#1, SSbD#2	SSbD#0, SSbD#1, SSbD#2	SSbD#0, SSbD#1, SSbD#2	SSbD#0, SSbD#1, SSbD#2
	CS1_04	CS1_08	CS1_26	CS1_18	CS1_20-1	CS1_20-2	CS1_20-3	CS1_20-4
	Polyol D	2-hydroxy-ethyl disulfide	Cystamine	N,N,N',N'-Tetrakis(2-hydroxyethyl) ethylenediamine (THEED)	Niax catalyst A1	Niax catalyst A1	Niax catalyst A1	Niax catalyst A1
Daphnia	1.00	1.98	1.90	1.00	1.10			
Zebrafish	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00				
QSARs	1.78	2.94	4.27	3.00	2.75	2.31	1.79	2.54
Ecotoxicity Score	0.93	1.64	2.05	1.33	1.92	2.31	1.79	2.54

Figure 5.1-1: Visualization of total ecotoxicity score for CS1 substances.

Scores of the catalysts can be compared for evaluation of hazard in an SSbD context. THEED (CS1_18) is has the lowest ecotoxicological hazard, whereas cystamine (CS1_26) has the highest hazard, but not so much higher than 2-hydroxyethylsulfidie (CS1_08)

5.2 Case Study 2

For Case Study 2 only for the group of hardeners QSARs could be calculated for all substances in the group. In addition, QSARs were calculated for four expected IAS and for four substances identified in leachates. The ingredient scores are shown in

Table 5.2-1 and Figure 5.2-1. All substances result in a relatively high toxicity score (above 2). Comparison of QSAR results with daphnia and zebrafish data results in the same ranking of substances. Like for CS1, also for CS2 the scores for QSARs are higher than for daphnia and zebrafish, as QSAR scores are based on the effect in the most sensitive species.

Table 5.2-1: Ecotoxicity scoring based on QSAR models and Daphnia and Zebrafish experiments for CS2 substances.

	SSbD#0	SSbD#1	N/A	All routes	SSbD#1	SSbD#0	SSbD#0	SSbD#0	SSbD#0	SSbD#0	SSbD#0
	CS2_14	CS2_02	CS2_15	CS2_45	CS2_46	CS2_47	CS2_48	CS2_41	CS2_42	CS2_43	CS2_44
	MDA	4-AFD	2-AFD	Bisphenol A	4-aminothiophenol	Formaldehyde	Aniline	2-Propanol, 1-chloro-	2-Propanol, 1-chloro-, phosphate (3:1)	Bis (1-chloro-2-propyl) (3-chloro-1-propyl) phosphate	Bis (3-chloro-1-propyl) (1-chloro-2-propyl) phosphate
Daphnia	3.20	3.40	3.52								
Zebrafish	0.47	2.60	3.21								
QSARs	3.88	5.10	5.09	3.72	5.29	3.25	3.96	3.56	6.36	5.96	5.98
Ecotoxicity score	2.52	3.70	3.94	3.72	5.29	3.25	3.96	3.56	6.36	5.96	5.98

Figure 5.2-1: Visualization of total ecotoxicity score for CS2 substances.

For calculation of the performance scores, the production routes as also considered for D4.3, were used. As the data availability was different, performance scores are also slightly different. The hardeners were all assessed with QSAR modelling. In addition, some expected NIAS were included. Formaldehyde and aniline could come from MDA, Bisphenol A could come from all A-parts and 4-aminothiophenol could come from 4-AFD and therefore also be present in all leachates. The remaining four substances (2-propanol, 1-chloro-2-propanol, 1-chloro-, phosphate (3:1), bis(1-chloro-2-propyl)(3-chloro-1-propyl)phosphate and bis(3-chloro-1-propyl)(1-chloro-2-propyl)phosphate) were found in leachate of the composite with TCPP and were therefore related to the reference route. This resulted in 3 performance scores: a reference (MDA, bisphenol A, formaldehyde, aniline and all NIAS),

an alternative with 4-AFD (4-AFD, bisphenol A and 4-aminothiophenol) and an alternative with 2-AFD (2-AFD and bisphenol A). Product scores are shown in Table 5.2-2.

Table 5.2-2: Performance score based on ecotoxicological hazard.

	reference with leachate	4-AFD + any A-part + leachate	2-AFD + any A-part
Ecotoxicity score	0.00	0.64	0.78

Comparison of the reference with the two alternative routes (using different hardeners) results in a lower ecotoxicity hazard score for the two alternative products. This can be related to the lower number of IAS and NIAS in both alternative routes compared to the reference route.

5.3 Case Study 3

For Case Study 3, QSARs were calculated for the identified IAS and NIAS. No hazard information from Daphnia or Zebrafish was available for these specific substances as in these test the migration samples were used. The scores are shown in Table 5.3-1 and Figure 5.3-1.

Table 5.3-1: Ecotoxicity scoring based on QSAR models and Daphnia and Zebrafish experiments for CS3 substances.

	All routes CS3_17	SSbD#0 CS3_18	SSbD#0 CS3_21	SSbD#0 CS3_22	SSbD#1 CS3_19	All routes CS3_23	All routes CS3_24	All routes CS3_20
	Caprolactam	Undecanoic acid	Oleamide	Erucamide	2,4-di-tert-butylphenol	Irgafos 168	Irganox 1076	Tris (2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl) phosphate
Daphnia								
Zebrafish								
QSAR	2.53	3.31	4.88	0.00	3.94	0.00	0.00	0.00
Ecotoxicity	2.53	3.31	4.88	0.00	3.94	0.00	0.00	0.00

For some substances (CS3_22, CS3_23, CS3_24 and CS3_20) the calculated PNEC was higher than the solubility in water, in such cases, the substance is considered without hazard, resulting in zero scores. All other identified IAS and NIAS resulted in a potential ecotoxicological hazard. Although an ecotoxicological hazard could be considered less relevant for food packaging material, it should be noted that the tests described in D4.3 did not give any effect due to the relatively high toxicity of the solvent. Therefore, potential human hazards could have been missed.

Figure 5.3-1: Visualization of total ecotoxicity score for CS3 substances.

Performance scores were calculated based on the origin of the IAS and NIAS, resulting in 4 performance scores. All routes resulted in a release of caprolactam, igraxox 168, irganox 1076 and tris(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl)phosphate. These substances were therefore used to calculate all performance scores. For the reference route, undecanoic acid, oleamide and erucamide were added. For PE/compat/PA 65 layers no other IAS or NIAS were added and for PE/compat/PA 129 and PE/PA 129 only 2,4-di-tertbutylphenol was added. This means that the latter two were calculated from the same substances, therefore resulting in the same score.

Table 5.3-2: Performance score based on ecotoxicological hazard.

Reference: PO/PA/compat 11 layers	PE/compat/PA 65 layers	PE/compat/PA 129 layers	PE/PA 129 layers
0.00	0.76	0.40	0.40

All substances that were detected in the migration samples have a potentially ecotoxicological hazard. As more substances were detected in the migration sample of the reference product, all alternatives have a better performance score.

6. Deviations from the workplan

Establishment of a relation between physical-chemical properties and hazard appeared not possible due to the many data gaps and resulting low number of data points. Details are described in chapter 3.

ConsExpo modelling of substances identified in CS3 migration samples was initially not planned, but found to be relevant during the course of the project (see paragraph 4.2.3).

7. Conclusions and perspectives

QSAR modelling focussed on ecotoxicological hazards of ingredients, NIAS and IAS. As insufficient information was available for all substances, a complete comparison between reference product and SSRbD alternative could not be made. Nevertheless, ecotoxicological hazard evaluation, using QSARs and the results of the daphnia and zebrafish experiments described in D4.3, resulted in the following outcomes.

Case study 1: All ingredients, except for polyol D (the only polyol assessed), resulted in a potential ecotoxicological hazard. The potential ecotoxicological hazard of the catalysts differed, where cystamine had the highest hazard score and THEED the lowest. A comparison between production routes could not be made due to a lack of data on all ingredients.

Case study 2: All substances assessed with QSAR modelling resulted in a potential ecotoxicological hazard. However, adding the ecotoxicological hazards scores for the reference route and alternative routes, showed that the total scores were lower (less hazardous) for the alternative routes.

Case study 3: For some substances the potential ecotoxicological hazard level was higher than the water solubility, resulting in no potential hazard. All other substances detected in the migration samples, were found to have a potential ecotoxicological hazard. Although an ecotoxicological hazard could be considered less relevant for food packaging material, it should be noted that the tests described in D4.3 did not give any effect due to the relatively high toxicity of the solvent. Therefore, potential human hazards could have been missed.

QSAR modelling results in PNECs for a range of species. The outcomes shown in the tables and used for scoring were based on the most sensitive species. For some substances this most sensitive species gave a much lower PNEC than the average of all species, indicating that there could be a large difference in sensitivity. It should be noted that the approach by selecting the most sensitive species results in a conservative outcome with respect to ecotoxicological hazard.

In general, QSARs modelling can provide valuable information for hazard evaluation in an SSbD context. Available data, for example in the ECHA database, is often limited, and QSAR modelling provides a valuable and relatively easy and low cost method to obtain initial information on potential hazard, before more labour and cost intensive methods, like in vitro assays, are applied. However, the applicability domain and the reliability of specific QSAR models can vary, so careful evaluation of the model for the purpose and evaluation of the outcomes is required.

Due to a lack of data on physical chemical properties, a relation with hazard could not be established.

The use of the ConsExpo tool for the evaluation of oral exposure for CS3 has demonstrated that it is possible to estimate exposure with this tool, provided that the substance to be assessed is known, along with its concentration in the packaging or in the simulant.

However, to assess the hazard associated with oral exposure, it is necessary to know the toxicological threshold, such as the TTC (Threshold of Toxicological Concern), an Acceptable Daily Intake (ADI), or a Tolerable Daily Intake (TDI).

In the case of substances authorized under the Food Contact Regulation 10/2011/EU, the hazard associated with ingestion can be easily managed by performing a migration test, quantifying the concentration in the simulant, and comparing this value with the specific migration limit (SML) set by the regulation, which is based on the toxicological threshold of the regulated substances.

8. References

All public deliverables (a.o. D4.2, D4.3, D4.5, D4.6 and D5.1) and raw and processed data can be found on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/surpass/records>; 10.5281/zenodo.15533038, or on the SURPASS website: <https://www.surpass-project.eu/public-deliverables>

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9. Appendices

Results of QSAR modelling can be found in the following appendices

Appendix 1: QSAR based PNEC as basis for SURPASS SCORE

Appendix 2.1: QSAR based PNECs for acute effects

Appendix 2.2: QSAR based PNECs for acute effects: FISH LC50 (mg/L)

Appendix 2.3: QSAR based PNECs for acute effects: DAPHNIA EC50 (mg/L)

Appendix 2.4: QSAR based PNECs for acute effects: ALGAE EC50 (mg/L)

Appendix 3.1: QSAR based PNECs for chronic effects

Appendix 3.2: QSAR based PNECs for chronic effects for FISH, DAPHNIA and ALGAE

Appendix 4: Predicted class or Mode of Action

More detailed information is available on ZENODO (<https://zenodo.org/communities/surpass/records/10.5281/zenodo.15533038>, SURPASS D4.4 Appendix – ECOTOX QSAR predictions).

Appendix 1: QSAR based PNEC as basis for SURPASS SCORE

SURPASS chemical identifier	SMILES	Name	CAS RN	LOWEST QSAR based PNEC ACUTE/10 or CHRONIC in mg/L	MODEL / SPECIES / DURATION giving LOWEST toxicity prediction?	GEO MEAN AQUATIC ACUTE10 or CHRONIC	r geo lo
CS1_04	CONFIDENTIAL	Polyol D	CONFIDENTIAL	1.66E+00	VEGA IRFMN - ALGAE ACUTE	7.40E+01	4.4
CS1_08	S(SCCO)CCO	Disulfide	1892-29-1	1.14E-01	VEGA IRFMN/Combase - DAPHNIA ACUTE	1.03E+01	9.0
CS1_26	S(SCCN)CCN	Cystamine	51-85-4	5.39E-03	VEGA IRFMN/Combase - DAPHNIA ACUTE	2.78E+00	5.1
CS1_18	N(CCN(CCO)CCO)(CCO)CCO	THEED	140-07-8	1.01E-01	VEGA IRFMN/Combase - DAPHNIA ACUTE	6.60E+01	6.5
CS1_20-1	O(CCN(C)C)CCN(C)C	Niix Catalyst	3033-62-3	1.80E-01	VEGA IRFMN/Combase - DAPHNIA ACUTE	6.86E+00	3.8

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SURPASS chemical identifier	SMILES	Name	CAS RN	LOWEST QSAR based PNEC ACUTE/10 or CHRONIC in mg/L	MODEL / SPECIES / DURATION giving LOWEST toxicity prediction?	GEO MEAN AQUATIC ACUTE10 or CHRONIC	r geo lo
CS1_20-2	<chem>OCC(OCC(O)C)C</chem>	Niax Catalyst	106-62-7	4.87E-01	VEGA NIC - FISH ACUTE	5.94E+01	1.2
CS1_20-3	<chem>OC(C)COCC(O)C</chem>	Niax Catalyst	110-98-5	1.61E+00	VEGA DEMETRA - DAPHNIA ACUTE	6.71E+01	4.1
CS1_20-4	<chem>OCC(OC(C)CO)C</chem>	Niax Catalyst	108-61-2	2.87E-01	IRFMN - DAPHNIA CHRONIC	4.04E+01	1.4
CS2_02	<chem>S(SC1=CC=C(N)C=C1)C2=CC=C(N)C=C2</chem>	4-AFD	722-27-0	7.90E-04	DTU SciQSAR Daphnia magna 48hr EC50	5.67E-02	7.1
CS2_14	<chem>C(C1=CC=C(N)C=C1)C2=CC=C(N)C=C2</chem>	MDA	101-77-9	1.33E-02	ECOSAR Daphnid CHRONIC NOEC	1.92E-01	1.4
CS2_15	<chem>S(SC1=C(N)C=CC=C1)C2=C(N)C=CC=C2</chem>	2-AFD	1141-88-4	8.16E-04	DTU SciQSAR Daphnia magna 48hr EC50	7.82E-02	9.5
CS2_45	<chem>OC1=CC=C(C=C1)C(C2=CC=C(O)C=C2)(C)C</chem>	Bisphenol A	80-05-7	1.90E-02	VEGA IRFMN/Combase - DAPHNIA ACUTE	2.26E-01	1.1
CS2_46	<chem>SC1=CC=C(N)C=C1</chem>	4-aminothiophenol	1193-02-8	5.09E-04	VEGA IRFMN - ALGAE ACUTE	1.88E-01	3.6

SURPASS chemical identifier	SMILES	Name	CAS RN	LOWEST QSAR based PNEC ACUTE/10 or CHRONIC in mg/L	MODEL / SPECIES / DURATION giving LOWEST toxicity prediction?	GEO MEAN AQUATIC ACUTE10 or CHRONIC	r geo lo
CS2_47	O=C	Formaldehyde	50-00-0	5.66E-02	ECOSAR Daphnid CHRONIC NOEC	9.78E-01	1.7
CS2_48	NC1=CC=CC=C1	Aniline	62-53-3	1.10E-02	ECOSAR Daphnid CHRONIC NOEC	3.84E-01	3.5
CS2_41	CICC(O)C	2-Propanol, 1-chloro-	127-00-4	2.75E-02	VEGA PROTOQSAR/ Combase - ALGAE ACUTE	1.06E+01	3.8
CS2_42	O=P(OC(C)CCI)(OC(C)CCI)OC(C)CCI	2-Propanol, 1-chloro-, phosphate (3:1)	13674-84-5	4.40E-05	VEGA DEMETRA - DAPHNIA ACUTE	1.03E-01	2.3
CS2_43	CC(CCI)OP(=O)(OCCCCI)OC(C)CCI	Bis(1-chloro-2-propyl)(3-chloro-1-propyl)phosphate	137909-40-1	1.10E-04	VEGA DEMETRA - DAPHNIA ACUTE	1.33E-01	1.2
CS2_44	CC(CCI)OP(=O)(OCCCCI)OCCCCI	Bis(3-chloro-1-propyl)(1-chloro-2-propyl)phosphate	137888-35-8	1.05E-04	VEGA DEMETRA - DAPHNIA ACUTE	1.63E-01	1.5
CS3_17	O=C1NCCCCC1	Caprolactam	105-60-2	2.97E-01	VEGA IRFMN/Combase - DAPHNIA ACUTE	5.76E+00	1.9

SURPASS chemical identifier	SMILES	Name	CAS RN	LOWEST QSAR based PNEC ACUTE/10 or CHRONIC in mg/L	MODEL / SPECIES / DURATION giving LOWEST toxicity prediction?	GEO MEAN AQUATIC ACUTE10 or CHRONIC	r geo lo
CS3_18	<chem>O=C(O)CCCCCCCCC</chem>	Undecanoic acid	112-37-8	4.90E-02	VEGA NIC - FISH ACUTE	4.64E-01	9.4
CS3_21	<chem>O=C(N)CCCCCCCC=CCCCCCCC</chem>	Oleamide	301-02-0	1.33E-03	ECOSAR FISH CHRONIC NOEC	1.23E-02	9.2
CS3_22	<chem>O=C(N)CCCCCCCCCCCC=CCCCCCCC</chem>	Erucamide	112-84-5	no effects at any dose	IRFMN - ALGAE CHRONIC	1.01E-02	
CS3_19	<chem>OC1=CC=C(C=C1C(C)(C)C(C)(C)C</chem>	2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol	96-76-4	1.15E-02	ECOSAR FISH CHRONIC NOEC	5.64E-02	4.8
CS3_23	<chem>O(C1=CC=C(C=C1C(C)(C)C(C)(C)C)P(OC2=CC=C(C=C2C(C)(C)C(C)(C)C)OC3=CC=C(C=C3C(C)(C)C(C)(C)C</chem>	Irgafos 168	31570-04-4	no effects at any dose	IRFMN - DAPHNIA CHRONIC	5.19E-04	
CS3_24	<chem>O=C(OCCCCCCCCCCCCCCCC)CCC=1C=C(C(O)=C(C1)C(C)(C)C(C)(C)C</chem>	Irganox 1076	2082-79-3	no effects at any dose	IRFMN - DAPHNIA CHRONIC	2.38E-03	
CS3_20	<chem>O=P(OC1=CC=C(C=C1C(C)(C)C(C)(C)C)(OC2=CC=C(C=C2C(C)(C)C(C)(C)C)OC3=CC=C(C=C3C(C)(C)C(C)(C)C</chem>	Tris(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl) phosphate	95906-11-9	no effects at any dose	IRFMN - DAPHNIA CHRONIC	9.10E-04	

Appendix 2.1: QSAR based PNECs for acute effects

SURPASS chemical identifier	Name	LOWEST ACUTE EC50 (mg/L) prediction		LOWEST ACUTE EC50 (mg/L)		LOWEST ACUTE EC50 (mg/L)		DAPHNIDS	ALGAE	ALGAE	
		SCORE-BASE	MODEL / SPECIES / DURATION giving LOWEST toxicity prediction?	AQUATIC	ratio geomean/lowest	FISH	FISH				
		LOWEST AQUATIC ACUTE mg/L		GEO MEAN AQUATIC ACUTE		LOWEST FISH ACUTE	GEOMEAN FISH ACUTE	LOWEST DAPHNID ACUTE	GEOMEAN DAPHNID ACUTE	LOWEST ALGAE ACUTE	GEOMEAN ALGAE ACUTE
CS1_04	Polyol D	1.66E+01	VEGA IRFMN - ALGAE ACUTE	2.48E+03	1.50E+02	2.78E+01	7.91E+03	3.05E+01	2.37E+03	1.66E+01	8.1E+01
CS1_08	Disulfide	1.14E+00	VEGA IRFMN/Combase - DAPHNIA ACUTE	1.03E+02	9.06E+01	2.65E+01	4.13E+02	1.14E+00	4.28E+01	2.29E+00	6.2E+01
CS1_26	Cystamine	5.39E-02	VEGA IRFMN/Combase - DAPHNIA ACUTE	2.78E+01	5.15E+02	3.76E+01	1.84E+02	5.39E-02	4.14E+00	1.95E+00	2.8E+01
CS1_18	THEED	1.01E+00	VEGA IRFMN/Combase - DAPHNIA ACUTE	6.60E+02	6.55E+02	1.39E+00	1.33E+03	1.01E+00	9.81E+02	2.47E+00	2.2E+01
CS1_20-1	Niax Catalyst	1.80E+00	VEGA IRFMN/Combase - DAPHNIA ACUTE	6.86E+01	3.82E+01	3.38E+01	2.96E+02	1.80E+00	3.05E+01	3.02E+00	3.5E+01
CS1_20-2	Niax Catalyst	4.87E+00	VEGA NIC - FISH ACUTE	7.63E+02	1.57E+02	4.87E+00	1.75E+03	2.23E+01	6.87E+02	4.82E+01	3.7E+01
CS1_20-3	Niax Catalyst	1.61E+01	VEGA DEMETRA - DAPHNIA ACUTE	8.66E+02	5.37E+01	3.93E+01	2.27E+03	1.61E+01	7.11E+02	4.82E+01	4.0E+01
CS1_20-4	Niax Catalyst	4.87E+00	VEGA NIC - FISH ACUTE	8.72E+02	1.79E+02	4.87E+00	2.28E+03	1.77E+01	7.16E+02	4.82E+01	4.0E+01

SURPASS chemical identifier	Name	LOWEST ACUTE EC50 (mg/L) prediction		LOWEST ACUTE EC50 (mg/L)		LOWEST ACUTE EC50 (mg/L)		DAPHNIDS	ALGAE	ALGAE	ALGAE
		SCORE-BASE	MODEL / SPECIES / DURATION giving LOWEST toxicity prediction?	AQUATIC	ratio geomean/lowest	FISH	FISH				
		LOWEST AQUATIC ACUTE mg/L		GEO MEAN AQUATIC ACUTE		LOWEST FISH ACUTE	GEOMEAN FISH ACUTE	LOWEST DAPHNID ACUTE	GEOMEAN DAPHNID ACUTE	LOWEST ALGAE ACUTE	GEOMEAN ALGAE ACUTE
CS2_02	4-AFD	7.90E-03	DTU SciQSAR Daphnia magna 48hr EC50	1.37E+00	1.73E+02	1.30E+00	4.00E+00	7.90E-03	2.93E-01	6.03E-02	2.93E-01
CS2_14	MDA	3.16E-01	DTU SciQSAR Daphnia magna 48hr EC50	5.87E+00	1.86E+01	3.95E+00	1.33E+01	3.16E-01	1.22E+00	4.67E+00	1.22E+00
CS2_15	2-AFD	8.16E-03	DTU SciQSAR Daphnia magna 48hr EC50	1.55E+00	1.90E+02	1.08E+00	3.85E+00	8.16E-03	4.41E-01	5.62E-02	2.93E-01
CS2_45	Bisphenol A	1.90E-01	VEGA IRFMN/Combase - DAPHNIA ACUTE	5.08E+00	2.68E+01	1.28E+00	3.85E+00	1.90E-01	4.95E+00	1.29E+00	6.88E+00
CS2_46	4-aminothiophenol	5.09E-03	VEGA IRFMN - ALGAE ACUTE	6.02E+00	1.18E+03	2.14E+00	2.32E+01	5.09E-03	4.88E-01	4.04E+00	1.90E+00
CS2_47	Formaldehyde	1.32E+00	VEGA IRFMN - FISH ACUTE	4.13E+01	3.13E+01	1.32E+00	1.62E+02	4.14E+00	2.84E+01	2.79E+00	1.90E+00
CS2_48	Aniline	1.17E+00	VEGA IRFMN/Combase - DAPHNIA ACUTE	2.29E+01	1.96E+01	2.69E+01	6.89E+01	1.17E+00	3.94E+00	5.10E+00	4.95E+00
CS2_41	2-Propanol, 1-chloro-	2.75E-01	VEGA PROTOQSAR/ Combase - ALGAE ACUTE	1.06E+02	3.85E+02	5.34E+00	2.76E+02	5.17E+00	8.95E+01	2.75E-01	4.95E+00
CS2_42	2-Propanol, 1-chloro-, phosphate (3:1)	4.40E-04	VEGA DEMETRA - DAPHNIA ACUTE	1.03E+00	2.33E+03	2.47E-01	4.51E+00	4.40E-04	5.06E-02	1.12E-01	4.95E+00

SURPASS chemical identifier	Name	LOWEST ACUTE EC50 (mg/L) prediction		LOWEST ACUTE EC50 (mg/L)		LOWEST ACUTE EC50 (mg/L)		DAPHNIDS	ALGAE	ALGAE	ALGAE
		SCORE-BASE	MODEL / SPECIES / DURATION giving LOWEST toxicity prediction?	AQUATIC	ratio geomean/lowest	FISH	FISH				
		LOWEST AQUATIC ACUTE mg/L		GEO MEAN AQUATIC ACUTE		LOWEST FISH ACUTE	GEOMEAN FISH ACUTE	LOWEST DAPHNID ACUTE	GEOMEAN DAPHNID ACUTE	LOWEST ALGAE ACUTE	GEOMEAN ALGAE ACUTE
CS2_43	Bis(1-chloro-2-propyl)(3-chloro-1-propyl)phosphate	1.10E-03	VEGA DEMTRA - DAPHNIA ACUTE	1.33E+00	1.21E+03	2.47E-01	4.17E+00	1.10E-03	1.23E-01	1.17E-01	4.0E-01
CS2_44	Bis(3-chloro-1-propyl)(1-chloro-2-propyl)phosphate	1.05E-03	VEGA DEMTRA - DAPHNIA ACUTE	1.63E+00	1.55E+03	2.47E-01	5.33E+00	1.05E-03	1.58E-01	1.26E-01	5.0E-01
CS3_17	Caprolactam	2.97E+00	VEGA IRFMN/Combase - DAPHNIA ACUTE	1.04E+02	3.50E+01	1.58E+01	1.66E+02	2.97E+00	4.23E+01	3.84E+00	1.0E+01
CS3_18	Undecanoic acid	4.90E-01	VEGA NIC - FISH ACUTE	7.24E+00	1.48E+01	4.90E-01	4.81E+00	1.38E+00	8.45E+00	1.26E+00	9.3E+00
CS3_21	Oleamide	no acute effects (log Kow)	VEGA IRFMN/Combase - FISH ACUTE	3.51E-01	#VALUE!	7.07E-03	1.21E-01	5.88E-02	5.54E-01	3.17E-01	6.0E-01
CS3_22	Erucamide	no acute effects (log Kow)	VEGA IRFMN/Combase - FISH ACUTE	1.01E-01	#VALUE!	9.51E-04	3.52E-02	2.50E-02	1.60E-01	2.98E-02	1.0E-01
CS3_19	2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol	no acute effects (log Kow)	VEGA IRFMN/Combase - DAPHNIA ACUTE	1.79E+00	#VALUE!	1.44E-01	1.40E+00	1.11E-01	8.99E-01	2.06E-01	4.5E-01
CS3_23	Irgafos 168	no acute effects (log Kow)	VEGA IRFMN/Combase - DAPHNIA ACUTE	5.19E-03	#VALUE!	1.86E-05	1.31E-02	2.57E-08	6.04E-05	2.98E-02	1.0E-01
CS3_24	Irganox 1076	no acute effects (log Kow)	EPA - FATHEAD MINNOW ACUTE	2.38E-02	#VALUE!	4.02E-05	1.20E-02	1.46E-04	5.33E-03	8.44E-03	2.0E-01

SURPASS chemical identifier	Name	LOWEST ACUTE EC50 (mg/L) prediction		LOWEST ACUTE EC50 (mg/L)		LOWEST ACUTE EC50 (mg/L)					
		SCORE-BASE		AQUATIC		FISH		DAPHNIDS		ALGAE	
		LOWEST AQUATIC ACUTE mg/L	MODEL / SPECIES / DURATION giving LOWEST toxicity prediction?	GEO MEAN AQUATIC ACUTE	ratio geomean/ lowest	LOWEST FISH ACUTE	GEOMEAN FISH ACUTE	LOWEST DAPHNID ACUTE	GEOMEAN DAPHNID ACUTE	LOWEST ALGAE ACUTE	GEO ALG ACUTE
CS3_20	Tris(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl) phosphate	no acute effects (log Kow)	VEGA IRFMN/Combase - DAPHNIA ACUTE	9.10E-03	#VALUE!	6.78E-06	5.25E-02	9.58E-08	4.72E-05	4.79E-02	3.

Appendix 2.2: QSAR based PNECs for acute effects: FISH LC50 (mg/L)

SURPASS chemical identifier	Name	ECOSAR Fish LC50 96hr	T.E.S.T. Fathead Minnow LC50 96 hr	DTU Battery Fathead Minnow LC50 96 hr	DTU Leadscope Fathead Minnow LC50 96 hr	DTU SciQSAR Fathead Minnow LC50 96 hr	VEGA KNN/read across - FISH ACUTE	VEGA NIC - FISH ACUTE	VEGA IRFMN - FISH ACUTE	VEGA IRFMN/Combase - FISH ACUTE	EPA - FATHEAD MINNOW ACUTE	VEGA KNN/IRFMN - FATHEAD MINNOW ACUTE	VEGA KNN/IRFMN - GUPPY ACUTE
CS1_04	Polyol D	1.44E+05	1.10E+04	1.15E+04	1.93E+04	3.81E+03	2.82E+04	2.54E+04	2.78E+01	3.66E+02	5.06E+03	1.97E+04	6.22E+04
CS1_08	Disulfide	3.99E+03	2.37E+02	-	1.46E+02	1.02E+03	-	1.69E+02	2.65E+01	1.04E+02	9.07E+01	5.86E+04	-
CS1_26	Cystamine	6.87E+02	7.40E+01	-	1.31E+02	6.04E+02	2.40E+02	3.91E+01	3.76E+01	7.98E+01	2.83E+02	1.42E+03	-
CS1_18	THEED	2.73E+05	1.26E+04	4.66E+03	3.73E+03	5.58E+03	1.07E+03	1.39E+00	2.49E+01	1.63E+01	3.49E+04	3.19E+03	-
CS1_20-1	Niax Catalyst	1.43E+03	8.64E+02	4.04E+02	9.62E+01	7.11E+02	1.00E+02	3.50E+01	3.38E+01	3.75E+01	2.85E+03	3.59E+03	-
CS1_20-2	Niax Catalyst	2.58E+04	6.92E+03	4.49E+03	7.74E+03	1.24E+03	9.33E+03	4.87E+00	1.69E+01	3.00E+02	1.25E+03	4.05E+04	9.28E+03
CS1_20-3	Niax Catalyst	2.58E+04	7.96E+03	4.68E+03	7.74E+03	1.63E+03	6.31E+03	6.88E+01	3.93E+01	1.98E+02	1.22E+03	4.05E+04	9.28E+03
CS1_20-4	Niax Catalyst	2.58E+04	8.78E+03	5.72E+03	1.03E+04	1.18E+03	2.75E+04	4.87E+00	3.93E+01	1.61E+02	1.50E+03	4.14E+04	2.38E+04
CS2_02	4-AFD	1.32E+01	1.30E+00	2.99E+00	4.17E+00	1.81E+00	2.69E+00	7.67E+01	2.00E+00	2.72E+00	4.31E+00	2.26E+00	-
CS2_14	MDA	1.63E+01	7.91E+00	1.64E+01	2.50E+01	7.79E+00	2.09E+01	1.17E+01	2.10E+01	3.95E+00	3.00E+01	9.06E+00	-
CS2_15	2-AFD	1.32E+01	1.08E+00	3.09E+00	4.17E+00	2.01E+00	2.75E+00	7.67E+01	3.22E+00	2.16E+00	3.59E+00	1.43E+00	-
CS2_45	Bisphenol A	1.28E+00	3.24E+00	3.84E+00	4.76E+00	2.91E+00	6.03E+00	5.47E+00	7.98E+00	2.08E+00	4.99E+00	4.55E+00	-
CS2_46	4-aminothiophenol	1.91E+01	N/A	4.97E+01	3.77E+01	6.16E+01	2.14E+00	2.33E+00	7.00E+00	3.86E+01	6.41E+01	7.53E+01	7.36E+01

SURPASS chemical identifier	Name	ECOSAR Fish LC50 96hr	T.E.S.T. Fathead Minnow LC50 96 hr	DTU Battery Fathead Minnow LC50 96 hr	DTU Leadscope Fathead Minnow LC50 96 hr	DTU SciQSA R Fathead Minnow LC50 96 hr	VEGA KNN/read across - FISH ACUTE	VEGA NIC - FISH ACUTE	VEGA IRFMN - FISH ACUTE	VEGA IRFMN/Combase - FISH ACUTE	EPA - FATHEAD MINNOW ACUTE	VEGA KNN/IRFMN - FATHEAD MINNOW ACUTE	VEGA KNN/IRFMN - GUPPY ACUTE
CS2_47	Formaldehyde	1.12E+01	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	2.75E+03	5.34E+02	1.32E+00	1.22E+02	1.81E+03	6.13E+02	-
CS2_48	Aniline	4.03E+01	8.09E+01	6.28E+01	5.15E+01	7.42E+01	7.08E+01	4.16E+01	2.69E+01	7.22E+01	1.90E+02	1.17E+02	1.14E+02
CS2_41	2-Propanol, 1-chloro-	1.62E+03	7.90E+02	-	1.50E+02	1.85E+02	2.45E+02	4.20E+01	5.34E+00	2.71E+02	4.10E+02	2.42E+02	1.36E+04
CS2_42	2-Propanol, 1-chloro-, phosphate (3:1)	1.52E+00	7.24E+00	-	1.66E+00	2.18E+01	1.74E+00	2.47E-01	1.43E+00	5.67E+01	2.01E+01	1.24E+01	-
CS2_43	Bis(1-chloro-2-propyl)(3-chloro-1-propyl)phosphate	1.45E+00	7.20E+00	N/A	N/A	N/A	1.82E+00	2.47E-01	1.37E+00	4.71E+01	2.42E+01	1.24E+01	-
CS2_44	Bis(3-chloro-1-propyl)(1-chloro-2-propyl)phosphate	1.38E+00	7.46E+00	N/A	N/A	N/A	7.59E+00	2.47E-01	2.14E+00	4.01E+01	3.19E+01	1.24E+01	-
CS3_17	Caprolactam	3.48E+02	2.27E+02	-	2.08E+02	5.07E+02	1.51E+02	4.11E+02	1.58E+01	2.01E+01	3.92E+02	2.42E+02	-
CS3_18	Undecanoic acid	8.58E+00	2.28E+00	1.43E+01	2.51E+01	3.48E+00	1.51E+01	4.90E-01	3.61E+00	7.41E+00	2.69E+00	1.07E+01	1.10E+00
CS3_21	Oleamide	>w.s	6.90E-02	-	2.82E-02	9.59E-03	1.41E+00	1.48E+00	4.74E-01	7.07E-03	1.58E-01	2.75E-01	-
CS3_22	Erucamide	>w.s	8.58E-03	-	1.95E-03	1.95E-03	4.57E-01	2.18E+00	5.29E-01	9.51E-04	1.54E-02	3.30E-01	-
CS3_19	2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol	1.44E-01	2.04E+00	1.80E+00	7.68E-01	2.82E+00	6.76E-01	2.85E+00	6.77E-01	6.99E+00	1.84E+00	7.15E-01	4.21E+00
CS3_23	Irgafos 168	>w.s	N/A	-	2.70E-04	2.70E-04	2.88E+00	7.60E+00	1.72E+00	1.32E-03	1.86E-05	-	-
CS3_24	Irganox 1076	>w.s	4.29E-03	-	2.21E-04	2.21E-04	8.71E+00	2.72E+00	1.23E+00	1.72E-04	4.02E-05	-	-
CS3_20	Tris(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl) phosphate	>w.s	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	2.88E+00	7.78E+00	1.58E+00	1.66E-03	6.78E-06	-	-

Appendix 2.3: QSAR based PNECs for acute effects: DAPHNIA EC50 (mg/L)

SURPASS chemical identifier	Name	ECOSAR Daphnid EC50 48hr	T.E.S.T. Daphnia magna EC50 48hr	DTU Battery Daphnia magna 48hr EC50	DTU Leadscope Daphnia magna 48hr EC50	DTU SciQSAR Daphnia magna 48hr EC50	VEGA EPA - DAPHNIA ACUTE	VEGA DEMETRA - DAPHNIA ACUTE	VEGA IRFMN - DAPHNIA ACUTE	VEGA IRFMN/Combase - DAPHNIA ACUTE
CS1_04	Polyol D	5.85E+07	6.30E+03	7.39E+02	3.62E+02	1.12E+03	1.01E+05	3.05E+01	9.86E+01	6.98E+01
CS1_08	Disulfide	1.94E+03	2.57E+02	-	2.59E+01	8.98E+01	2.68E+02	1.40E+00	2.28E+01	1.14E+00
CS1_26	Cystamine	6.43E+01	1.04E+01	-	2.06E+01	1.10E+00	2.35E+00	3.10E+00	1.45E+01	5.39E-02
CS1_18	THEED	1.67E+04	2.01E+04	2.51E+03	5.48E+02	4.46E+03	2.47E+05	3.41E+01	4.82E+01	1.01E+00
CS1_20-1	Niax Catalyst	1.27E+02	5.83E+01	3.36E+01	2.74E+01	3.98E+01	4.95E+01	8.60E+00	1.08E+02	1.80E+00
CS1_20-2	Niax Catalyst	1.15E+04	2.48E+03	2.18E+03	3.48E+03	8.85E+02	1.69E+03	2.68E+01	1.77E+02	2.23E+01
CS1_20-3	Niax Catalyst	1.15E+04	3.36E+03	2.34E+03	3.48E+03	1.20E+03	1.94E+03	1.61E+01	1.61E+02	2.44E+01
CS1_20-4	Niax Catalyst	1.15E+04	2.21E+03	2.50E+03	3.48E+03	1.51E+03	1.54E+03	1.77E+01	2.23E+02	2.44E+01
CS2_02	4-AFD	1.95E+00	1.31E+00	9.25E-01	1.84E+00	7.90E-03	1.57E-01	1.84E-01	9.65E-01	1.68E-02
CS2_14	MDA	1.85E+00	2.97E+00	1.34E+00	2.36E+00	3.16E-01	7.71E-01	6.87E-01	5.71E+00	3.69E-01
CS2_15	2-AFD	1.95E+00	5.00E-01	9.25E-01	1.84E+00	8.16E-03	1.57E-01	2.72E-01	3.75E+00	2.91E-01
CS2_45	Bisphenol A	4.15E+00	1.58E+00	5.19E+00	1.35E+00	9.03E+00	2.13E+01	7.73E+01	1.37E+01	1.90E-01

CS2_46	4-aminothiophenol	1.49E+0 0	N/A	5.68E+0 0	1.12E+01	1.66E-01	5.09E-03	5.71E-01	6.71E-01	1.04E-01
CS2_47	Formaldehyde	1.20E+0 1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	2.61E+02	1.50E+01	4.14E+00	9.49E+01
CS2_48	Aniline	1.67E+0 0	2.97E+0 0	1.01E+0 1	1.38E+01	6.35E+0 0	7.56E+00	1.73E+00	3.38E+00	1.17E+00
CS2_41	2-Propanol, 1-chloro-	8.04E+0 2	2.46E+0 2	-	3.15E+01	1.37E+0 2	3.83E+02	5.17E+00	2.10E+01	1.16E+02
CS2_42	2-Propanol, 1-chloro-, phosphate (3:1)	9.90E-02	9.94E-03	2.04E-02	2.72E-02	1.37E-02	2.59E-01	4.40E-04	2.20E+00	1.16E+00
CS2_43	Bis(1-chloro-2-propyl)(3- chloro-1-propyl)phosphate	9.80E-02	1.93E-02	N/A	N/A	N/A	2.31E-01	1.10E-03	5.67E+00	1.27E+00
CS2_44	Bis(3-chloro-1-propyl)(1- chloro-2-propyl)phosphate	9.80E-02	3.73E-02	N/A	N/A	N/A	2.06E-01	1.05E-03	1.42E+01	1.39E+00
CS3_17	Caprolactam	4.15E+0 2	7.04E+0 1	-	2.71E+01	5.42E+0 2	1.53E+01	1.46E+01	3.58E+01	2.97E+00
CS3_18	Undecanoic acid	6.14E+0 0	1.16E+0 1	1.03E+0 1	1.26E+01	7.95E+0 0	1.99E+01	1.45E+01	1.38E+00	7.58E+00
CS3_21	Oleamide	>w.s	1.15E+0 0	-	1.22E+00	1.22E+0 0	9.31E-01	2.45E-01	5.88E-02	7.07E-01
CS3_22	Erucamide	>w.s	7.40E-01	-	1.16E-01	2.63E-01	3.61E-01	7.55E-02	2.50E-02	1.77E-01
CS3_19	2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol	2.81E-01	5.60E-01	1.50E+0 0	9.28E-01	2.07E+0 0	6.83E-01	2.54E+01	4.41E-01	1.11E-01
CS3_23	Irgafos 168	>w.s	N/A	-	3.88E-05	5.30E-02	4.47E-07	1.48E-04	1.38E-02	2.57E-08
CS3_24	Irganox 1076	>w.s	9.46E-02	-	4.78E-04	2.07E-02	4.52E-03	9.22E-03	2.16E-02	1.46E-04
CS3_20	Tris(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl) phosphate	>w.s	7.03E-04	N/A	N/A	N/A	1.07E-07	2.64E-03	1.23E-02	9.58E-08

>w.s. = higher than water solubility

N/A = not available

Lowest PNECs are highlighted.

Appendix 2.4: QSAR based PNECs for acute effects: ALGAE EC50 (mg/L)

SURPASS chemical identifier	Name	ECOSAR Algae EC50 96hr	T.E.S.T. T. Pyriformis IGC50 48hr	DTU Battery Pseudokirchneriella s. 72h EC50 (mg/L)	DTU Leadscope Pseudokirchneriella s. 72h EC50 (mg/L)	DTU SciQSAR Pseudokirchneriella s. 72h EC50 (mg/L)	VEGA IRFMN - ALGAE ACUTE	VEGA PROTOQSAR/ Combase - ALGAE ACUTE
CS1_04	Polyol D	1.80E+03	2.89E+04	1.62E+03	4.99E+02	2.73E+03	1.66E+01	1.29E+02
CS1_08	Disulfide	7.65E+02	N/A	-	6.70E+01	2.32E+02	3.54E+01	2.29E+00
CS1_26	Cystamine	8.57E+01	N/A	-	6.18E+01	6.01E+01	2.85E+01	1.95E+00
CS1_18	THEED	5.17E+04	1.31E+04	-	8.28E+01	3.19E+02	2.47E+00	2.63E+00
CS1_20-1	Niax Catalyst	1.88E+02	1.23E+03	1.73E+01	2.97E+01	4.95E+00	4.18E+01	3.02E+00
CS1_20-2	Niax Catalyst	3.13E+03	5.08E+03	2.93E+02	4.82E+01	5.37E+02	5.42E+01	1.45E+02
CS1_20-3	Niax Catalyst	3.13E+03	4.82E+03	3.44E+02	4.82E+01	6.40E+02	6.56E+01	1.62E+02
CS1_20-4	Niax Catalyst	3.13E+03	5.40E+03	3.97E+02	4.82E+01	7.46E+02	5.78E+01	1.32E+02
CS2_02	4-AFD	4.68E+00	N/A	6.26E+00	8.44E+00	4.08E+00	1.77E+00	6.03E-02
CS2_14	MDA	4.67E+00	1.83E+01	1.05E+01	1.26E+01	8.34E+00	1.20E+01	4.17E+01
CS2_15	2-AFD	4.68E+00	N/A	6.24E+00	8.44E+00	4.04E+00	2.07E+00	5.62E-02
CS2_45	Bisphenol A	1.33E+00	5.30E+00	2.56E+01	2.38E+01	2.74E+01	4.79E+00	1.29E+00
CS2_46	4-aminothiophenol	4.04E+00	2.20E+01	2.80E+01	1.79E+01	3.80E+01	7.87E+00	7.41E+01
CS2_47	Formaldehyde	5.87E+00	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	2.79E+00	2.19E+02
CS2_48	Aniline	5.10E+00	2.03E+02	3.66E+01	1.70E+01	5.63E+01	1.10E+02	8.71E+01
CS2_41	2-Propanol, 1-chloro-	3.42E+02	8.14E+02	-	6.96E+01	1.06E+02	2.23E+01	2.75E-01
CS2_42	2-Propanol, 1-chloro-, phosphate (3:1)	1.07E+01	1.51E+02	-	1.80E+01	8.57E-01	4.10E+00	1.12E-01
CS2_43	Bis(1-chloro-2-propyl)(3-chloro-1-propyl)phosphate	9.47E+00	1.70E+02	N/A	N/A	N/A	2.38E+00	1.17E-01
CS2_44	Bis(3-chloro-1-propyl)(1-chloro-2-propyl)phosphate	8.38E+00	2.38E+02	N/A	N/A	N/A	2.83E+00	1.26E-01

SURPASS chemical identifier	Name	ECOSAR Algae EC50 96hr	T.E.S.T. T. Pyriformis IGC50 48hr	DTU Battery Pseudokirchneriella s. 72h EC50 (mg/L)	DTU Leadscope Pseudokirchneriella s. 72h EC50 (mg/L)	DTU SciQSAR Pseudokirchneriella s. 72h EC50 (mg/L)	VEGA IRFMN - ALGAE ACUTE	VEGA PROTOQSAR/ Combase - ALGAE ACUTE
CS3_17	Caprolactam	2.60E+01	N/A	-	7.90E+01	5.58E+04	3.84E+00	2.51E+02
CS3_18	Undecanoic acid	1.19E+01	2.40E+01	4.07E+01	7.74E+01	3.98E+00	1.39E+00	1.26E+00
CS3_21	Oleamide	>w.s	6.00E-01	1.03E+00	6.61E-01	1.40E+00	3.17E-01	3.80E-01
CS3_22	Erucamide	>w.s	7.50E-02	-	2.98E-02	5.94E-01	5.06E-01	3.02E-01
CS3_19	2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol	2.06E-01	6.40E+00	2.60E+01	1.90E+01	3.31E+01	9.96E-01	1.86E+00
CS3_23	Irgafos 168	>w.s	N/A	-	2.98E-02	5.94E-01	1.00E+00	5.50E-02
CS3_24	Irganox 1076	>w.s	8.86E-03	-	2.49E-01	8.44E-03	1.69E+00	1.32E+01
CS3_20	Tris(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl) phosphate	>w.s	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1.93E+00	4.79E-02

Appendix 3.1: QSAR based PNECs for chronic effects

SURPASS chemical identifier	Name	CHRONIC NOEC (mg/L) prediction		LOWEST CHRONIC NOEC (mg/L)		LOWEST CHRONIC NOEC (mg/L)			ALGAE	G	AL	CH	
		SCORE-BASE	MODEL / SPECIES / DURATION giving LOWEST toxicity prediction?	AQUATIC	ratio geomean/lowest	FISH	DAPHNIDS	GEOMEAN DAPHNID CHRONIC					LOWEST ALGAE CHRONIC
		LOWEST AQUATIC CHRONIC		GEO MEAN AQUATIC CHRONIC		LOWEST FISH CHRONIC							
CS1_04	Polyol D	4.83E+00	IRFMN - DAPHNIA CHRONIC	7.40E+01	1.53E+01	1.14E+01	2.49E+02	4.83E+00	2.53E+01	5.34E+00			
CS1_08	Disulfide	4.65E-01	IRFMN - DAPHNIA CHRONIC	1.42E+01	3.05E+01	2.41E+00	2.13E+01	4.65E-01	5.75E+00	6.62E+00			
CS1_26	Cystamine	5.52E-01	IRFMN - DAPHNIA CHRONIC	4.34E+00	7.86E+00	2.20E+00	1.03E+01	5.52E-01	1.15E+00	3.42E+00			
CS1_18	THEED	3.50E-01	IRFMN - FISH CHRONIC	7.87E+01	2.25E+02	3.50E-01	1.57E+02	2.10E+00	2.95E+01	1.82E+00			
CS1_20-1	Niax Catalyst	1.15E+00	IRFMN - FISH CHRONIC	7.74E+00	6.73E+00	1.15E+00	1.17E+01	4.53E+00	6.03E+00	1.49E+00			
CS1_20-2	Niax Catalyst	3.62E+00	IRFMN - FISH CHRONIC	5.94E+01	1.64E+01	3.62E+00	6.29E+01	5.59E+00	4.29E+01	2.20E+01			
CS1_20-3	Niax Catalyst	5.59E+00	IRFMN - DAPHNIA CHRONIC	6.71E+01	1.20E+01	6.11E+00	8.17E+01	5.59E+00	4.29E+01	2.71E+01			
CS1_20-4	Niax Catalyst	2.87E-01	IRFMN - DAPHNIA CHRONIC	4.04E+01	1.41E+02	5.55E+00	7.79E+01	2.87E-01	9.71E+00	2.79E+01			
CS2_02	4-AFD	4.84E-03	IRFMN - DAPHNIA CHRONIC	5.67E-02	1.17E+01	6.29E-02	8.58E-02	4.84E-03	8.36E-03	1.07E-01			
CS2_14	MDA	1.33E-02	ECOSAR Daphnid CHRONIC NOEC	1.92E-01	1.44E+01	8.78E-02	9.36E-02	1.33E-02	4.57E-02	6.81E-01			
CS2_15	2-AFD	1.44E-02	ECOSAR Daphnid CHRONIC NOEC	7.82E-02	5.42E+00	6.29E-02	9.28E-02	1.44E-02	2.52E-02	6.87E-02			
CS2_45	Bisphenol A	4.43E-02	IRFMN - FISH CHRONIC	2.26E-01	5.11E+00	4.43E-02	1.19E-01	3.56E-01	4.79E-01	1.31E-01			
CS2_46	4-aminothiophenol	6.41E-03	IRFMN - DAPHNIA CHRONIC	1.88E-01	2.93E+01	1.22E-01	8.68E-01	6.41E-03	8.16E-03	6.99E-01			

SURPASS chemical identifier	Name	CHRONIC NOEC (mg/L) prediction		LOWEST CHRONIC NOEC (mg/L)		LOWEST CHRONIC NOEC (mg/L)					
		SCORE-BASE	MODEL / SPECIES / DURATION giving LOWEST toxicity prediction?	AQUATIC	ratio geomean/lowest	FISH		DAPHNIDS			
		LOWEST AQUATIC CHRONIC		GEO MEAN AQUATIC CHRONIC		LOWEST FISH CHRONIC	GEOMEAN FISH CHRONIC	LOWEST DAPHNID CHRONIC	GEOMEAN DAPHNID CHRONIC	LOWEST ALGAE CHRONIC	
CS2_47	Formaldehyde	5.66E-02	ECOSAR Daphnid CHRONIC NOEC	9.78E-01	1.73E+01	6.20E-01	1.14E+00	5.66E-02	2.88E-01	1.03E+00	
CS2_48	Aniline	1.10E-02	ECOSAR Daphnid CHRONIC NOEC	3.84E-01	3.50E+01	3.42E-01	1.18E+00	1.10E-02	2.31E-02	1.18E+00	
CS2_41	2-Propanol, 1-chloro-	2.59E+00	IRFMN - DAPHNIA CHRONIC	1.66E+01	6.42E+00	1.12E+01	2.95E+01	2.59E+00	8.97E+00	7.90E+00	
CS2_42	2-Propanol, 1-chloro-, phosphate (3:1)	2.94E-03	ECOSAR FISH CHRONIC NOEC	3.86E-01	1.31E+02	2.94E-03	1.92E-02	9.62E-01	1.34E+00	2.05E+00	
CS2_43	Bis(1-chloro-2-propyl)(3-chloro-1-propyl)phosphate	2.89E-03	ECOSAR FISH CHRONIC NOEC	3.89E-01	1.35E+02	2.89E-03	2.15E-02	1.27E+00	1.45E+00	1.83E+00	
CS2_44	Bis(3-chloro-1-propyl)(1-chloro-2-propyl)phosphate	2.83E-03	ECOSAR FISH CHRONIC NOEC	3.79E-01	1.34E+02	2.83E-03	1.94E-02	1.39E+00	1.42E+00	1.63E+00	
CS3_17	Caprolactam	1.46E+00	ECOSAR FISH CHRONIC NOEC	5.76E+00	3.94E+00	1.46E+00	3.70E+00	7.82E+00	1.38E+01	2.64E+00	
CS3_18	Undecanoic acid	1.29E-01	IRFMN - FISH CHRONIC	4.64E-01	3.60E+00	1.29E-01	2.86E-01	2.04E-01	3.67E-01	3.02E-01	
CS3_21	Oleamide	1.33E-03	ECOSAR FISH CHRONIC NOEC	1.23E-02	9.28E+00	1.33E-03	6.68E-03	3.35E-03	1.85E-02	7.80E-03	
CS3_22	Erucamide	no chronic effects (log Kow)	IRFMN - ALGAE CHRONIC	2.99E-02	#VALUE!	4.96E-02	4.96E-02	5.11E-02	5.11E-02	1.06E-02	
CS3_19	2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol	1.15E-02	ECOSAR FISH CHRONIC NOEC	5.64E-02	4.89E+00	1.15E-02	4.12E-02	1.79E-02	5.23E-02	3.87E-02	
CS3_23	Irgafos 168	no chronic effects (log Kow)	IRFMN - DAPHNIA CHRONIC	1.24E-01	#VALUE!	2.38E-01	2.38E-01	2.63E-03	2.63E-03	3.02E+00	
CS3_24	Irganox 1076	no chronic effects (log Kow)	IRFMN - DAPHNIA CHRONIC	1.09E-01	#VALUE!	1.60E-01	1.60E-01	4.62E-03	4.62E-03	1.76E+00	

SURPASS chemical identifier	Name	CHRONIC NOEC (mg/L) prediction		LOWEST CHRONIC NOEC (mg/L)		LOWEST CHRONIC NOEC (mg/L)			ALGAE	G	
		SCORE-BASE	MODEL / SPECIES / DURATION giving LOWEST toxicity prediction?	AQUATIC	ratio geomean/lowest	FISH	DAPHNIDS	ALGAE			
CS3_20	Tris(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl) phosphate	no chronic effects (log Kow)	IRFMN - DAPHNIA CHRONIC	1.08E-01	#VALUE!	2.43E-01	2.43E-01	1.70E-03	1.70E-03	3.05E+00	

Appendix 3.2: QSAR based PNECs for chronic effects for FISH, DAPHNIA and ALGAE

SURPASS chemical identifier	Name	CHRONIC NOEC (mg/L)		DAPHNIA		ALGAE	
		ECOSAR FISH CHRONIC NOEC	IRFMN - FISH CHRONIC	ECOSAR Daphnid CHRONIC NOEC	IRFMN - DAPHNIA CHRONIC	ECOSAR Algae CHRONICNOEC 96 hr	IRFMN - ALGAE CHRONIC
CS1_04	Polyol D	5.47E+03	1.14E+01	1.33E+02	4.83E+00	7.70E+02	5.34E+00
CS1_08	Disulfide	1.88E+02	2.41E+00	7.12E+01	4.65E-01	8.20E+01	6.62E+00
CS1_26	Cystamine	4.84E+01	2.20E+00	2.41E+00	5.52E-01	1.38E+01	3.42E+00
CS1_18	THEED	7.04E+04	3.50E-01	4.13E+02	2.10E+00	6.12E+03	1.82E+00
CS1_20-1	Niax Catalyst	1.18E+02	1.15E+00	4.53E+00	8.03E+00	2.91E+01	1.49E+00
CS1_20-2	Niax Catalyst	1.09E+03	3.62E+00	3.29E+02	5.59E+00	2.75E+02	2.20E+01
CS1_20-3	Niax Catalyst	1.09E+03	6.11E+00	3.29E+02	5.59E+00	2.75E+02	2.71E+01
CS1_20-4	Niax Catalyst	1.09E+03	5.55E+00	3.29E+02	2.87E-01	2.75E+02	2.79E+01
CS2_02	4-AFD	6.29E-02	1.17E-01	1.44E-02	4.84E-03	6.06E-01	1.07E-01

SURPASS chemical identifier	Name	CHRONIC NOEC (mg/L)					
		FISH		DAPHNIA		ALGAE	
		ECOSAR FISH CHRONIC NOEC	IRFMN - FISH CHRONIC	ECOSAR Daphnid CHRONIC NOEC	IRFMN - DAPHNIA CHRONIC	ECOSAR Algae CHRONICNOEC 96 hr	IRFMN - ALGAE CHRONIC
CS2_14	MDA	8.78E-02	9.99E-02	1.33E-02	1.57E-01	6.81E-01	3.99E+00
CS2_15	2-AFD	6.29E-02	1.37E-01	1.44E-02	4.41E-02	6.06E-01	6.87E-02
CS2_45	Bisphenol A	3.18E-01	4.43E-02	3.56E-01	6.43E-01	1.31E-01	3.19E-01
CS2_46	4-aminothiophenol	1.22E-01	6.19E+00	1.04E-02	6.41E-03	6.99E-01	1.25E+00
CS2_47	Formaldehyde	2.09E+00	6.20E-01	5.66E-02	1.47E+00	1.03E+00	7.91E+00
CS2_48	Aniline	3.42E-01	4.04E+00	1.10E-02	4.88E-02	1.18E+00	3.69E+00
CS2_41	2-Propanol, 1-chloro-	7.79E+01	1.12E+01	3.11E+01	2.59E+00	3.82E+01	7.90E+00
CS2_42	2-Propanol, 1-chloro-, phosphate (3:1)	2.94E-03	1.26E-01	1.88E+00	9.62E-01	2.05E+00	2.40E+00
CS2_43	Bis(1-chloro-2-propyl)(3-chloro-1-propyl)phosphate	2.89E-03	1.60E-01	1.65E+00	1.27E+00	1.83E+00	1.96E+00
CS2_44	Bis(3-chloro-1-propyl)(1-chloro-2-propyl)phosphate	2.83E-03	1.33E-01	1.45E+00	1.39E+00	1.63E+00	2.39E+00
CS3_17	Caprolactam	1.46E+00	9.39E+00	2.42E+01	7.82E+00	5.31E+00	2.64E+00
CS3_18	Undecanoic acid	6.35E-01	1.29E-01	6.58E-01	2.04E-01	3.01E+00	3.02E-01
CS3_21	Oleamide	1.33E-03	3.36E-02	3.35E-03	1.02E-01	2.94E-02	7.80E-03
CS3_22	Erucamide	>w.s	4.96E-02	>w.s	5.11E-02	>w.s	1.06E-02
CS3_19	2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol	1.15E-02	1.47E-01	1.79E-02	1.53E-01	3.87E-02	1.79E-01
CS3_23	Irgafos 168	>w.s	2.38E-01	>w.s	2.63E-03	>w.s	3.02E+00
CS3_24	Irganox 1076	>w.s	1.60E-01	>w.s	4.62E-03	>w.s	1.76E+00
CS3_20	Tris(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl) phosphate	>w.s	2.43E-01	>w.s	1.70E-03	>w.s	3.05E+00

Appendix 4: Predicted class or Mode of Action

SURPASS chemical identifier		PREDICTED CLASS/MOA		MoA Classification (IRFMN) - prediction	Verhaar classification (TOXTREE) - prediction
		ECOSAR	MOA toxicity classification (EPA T.E.S.T.) - prediction		
CS1_04	Polyol D	neutral organics	Narcosis	No MoA	Class 5 (Not possible to classify according to these rules)
CS1_08	Disulfide	neutral organics	Narcosis	No MoA	Class 3 (unspecific reactivity)
CS1_26	Cystamine	aliphatic amines	Narcosis	No MoA	Class 3 (unspecific reactivity)
CS1_18	THEED	aliphatic amines	Narcosis	No MoA	Class 5 (Not possible to classify according to these rules)
CS1_20-1	Niax Catalyst	aliphatic amines	Narcosis	No MoA	Class 5 (Not possible to classify according to these rules)
CS1_20-2	Niax Catalyst	neutrol organics	Narcosis	No MoA	Class 1 (narcosis or baseline toxicity)
CS1_20-3	Niax Catalyst	neutral organics	Narcosis	No MoA	Class 1 (narcosis or baseline toxicity)
CS1_20-4	Niax Catalyst	neutral organics	Narcosis	No MoA	Class 1 (narcosis or baseline toxicity)
CS2_02	4-AFD	Anilines (unhindered)	Narcosis	No MoA	Class 3 (unspecific reactivity)
CS2_14	MDA	Anilines (unhindered)	Narcosis	No MoA	Class 5 (Not possible to classify according to these rules)
CS2_15	2-AFD	Anilines (unhindered)	Narcosis	No MoA	Class 3 (unspecific reactivity)
CS2_45	Bisphenol A	Phenols, Poly	Narcosis	No MoA	Class 5 (Not possible to classify according to these rules)
CS2_46	4-aminothiophenol	Anilines (unhindered)	Narcosis	No MoA	Class 5 (Not possible to classify according to these rules)
CS2_47	Formaldehyde	Aldehydes (mono)	Reactivity	No MoA	Class 3 (unspecific reactivity)

SURPASS chemical identifier		PREDICTED CLASS/MOA		MoA Classification (IRFMN) - prediction	Verhaar classification (TOXTREE) - prediction
		ECOSAR	MOA toxicity classification (EPA T.E.S.T.) - prediction		
CS2_48	Aniline	Anilines (unhindered)	Narcosis	No MoA	Class 5 (Not possible to classify according to these rules)
CS2_41	2-Propanol, 1-chloro-	neutral organics	Narcosis	No MoA	Class 1 (narcosis or baseline toxicity)
CS2_42	2-Propanol, 1-chloro-, phosphate (3:1)	Esters (phosphate)	AChE Inhibition	Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) inhibitors_AChE(-) (chemical group: Organophosphate)	Class 5 (Not possible to classify according to these rules)
CS2_43	Bis(1-chloro-2-propyl)(3-chloro-1-propyl)phosphate	Esters (phosphate)	AChE Inhibition	Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) inhibitors_AChE(-) (chemical group: Organophosphate)	Class 5 (Not possible to classify according to these rules)
CS2_44	Bis(3-chloro-1-propyl)(1-chloro-2-propyl)phosphate	Esters (phosphate)	AChE Inhibition	Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) inhibitors_AChE(-) (chemical group: Organophosphate)	Class 5 (Not possible to classify according to these rules)
CS3_17	Caprolactam	Amides	Narcosis	No MoA	Class 5 (Not possible to classify according to these rules)
CS3_18	Undecanoic acid	neutral organics	Narcosis	No MoA	Class 1 (narcosis or baseline toxicity)
CS3_21	Oleamide	Amides	Narcosis	No MoA	Class 5 (Not possible to classify according to these rules)
CS3_22	Erucamide	Amides	Narcosis	No MoA	Class 5 (Not possible to classify according to these rules)
CS3_19	2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol	Phenols	Narcosis	No MoA	Class 5 (Not possible to classify according to these rules)
CS3_23	Irgafos 168	neutral organics	Neurotoxicity	No MoA	Class 5 (Not possible to classify according to these rules)
CS3_24	Irganox 1076	unhindered vinyl alcohol	Narcosis	No MoA	Class 5 (Not possible to classify according to these rules)
CS3_20	Tris(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl) phosphate	Esters, Phosphates Inert substitutions	Neurotoxicity	Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) inhibitors_AChE(-) (chemical group: Organophosphate)	Class 4 (compounds and groups of compounds acting by a specific mechanism)